

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

(Experimental mass spectrometric and theoretical quantum chemical data)

N-glycans from fetuin

N-glycans from IgG

O-glycans from fetuin

(Continued as Figure S1.)

Complex,
multyantennary derivatives:

Complex (multyantennary) N-glycans from IgG:

Figure S1. Symbolic diagrams of N-glycans according to Harvey and co-workers [16,71,72,98]; multiply charged N-glycans from feutin and IgG; their chromatographic retention times (RTs)[mins] [11,12,20,21,93,S1–S4]; symbols and chemical diagrams of major carbohydrate monomers of N-glycans.

$(\text{GlcNAc})_2(\text{Man})_3$

Figure S2. Symbolic and chemical diagrams of $(\text{GlcNAc})_2(\text{Man})_5$ derivatized with 2-aminobenzamide adapted from [99]; the major fragment paths are presented according to nomenclature of carbohydrates by Dommon and Costello [95]; the bond cleavage has been observed under positive ESI polarity [99]; chemical diagrams of most probable analytes **(2)**, **(5d)**, **(9a)**, **(10d)**, (11d) and **(13d)** determined in this study.

Figure S3. Fragment reactions of high mannose glycan labelled with IPC and 2-AB; symbolic representation of the carbohydrate subunits and analyte 2D chemical diagram (see reference [114] in the main text.)

Figure S4. Fragment reactions of high mannose glycan; symbolic representation of the carbohydrate subunits and analyte 2D chemical diagram of mass spectrometric species

Figure S5. Fragment reactions of high mannose glycan (1); symbolic representation of carbohydrate subunits and analyte 2D chemical diagram of mass spectrometric species.

Figure S6. Screenshot of automated annotation of high Man-glycan glycan according to GlycoWorkbench software [105]

(Continued)

Figure S7. Mass spectrometric ion abundance [%] with respect to short span of measurement scan time as well as mass spectra of analytes (1), (2), (5), (8), (12) and (13); symbolic diagrams of molecular structures annotated according to annotation software [105] with score of probability of the structural assignment in [%]

Figure S8. Fragmentation scheme of complex N-glycans (A) schematic relation between D''_{SD} and D_{QC} parameters of equations (2) and (3) illustrating the logical consequence of our stochastic dynamic theory and its application to determine 3D structurally analytes.

Figure S9. Mass spectrometric ion abundance [%] with respect to short span of measurement scan time as well as mass spectra of analyte (9); symbolic diagrams of molecular structures annotated according to annotation software [105] with score of probability of the structural assignment in [%]

Figure S10. Mass spectrometric ion abundance [%] with respect to short span of measurement scan time as well as mass spectra of analytes (6) (A) and (7) (B); symbolic diagrams of molecular structures annotated according to [105] with score of probability of structural assignment in [%]; 2D chemical diagrams of the fragment species.

Figure S11. Mass spectrometric ion abundance [%] with respect to short span of measurement scan time as well as mass spectra of analytes (10) and (11); symbolic diagrams of molecular structures annotated according to [135,136] and annotation software [105] with score of probability of the structural assignment in [%]

Figure S12. Average mass spectra of carbohydrates depending on scan ID of experimental dataset (see reference [80]; main text.)

Figure S13. Mass spectrometric ion abundance [%] with respect to short span of measurement scan time as well as mass spectra of analytes (4), (10) and (11); symbolic diagrams of molecular structures annotated according to annotation software [105] with score of probability of the structural assignment in [%]

Figure S14. Correlation between measurable variables m/z and total intensity (I) [arb.units] as well as D^{SD} parameters [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] of equation (2) of glycans (6) and (7); chemometrics.

Figure S15. Lactone formation of carbodiimides according to work [6].

Figure S16. Correlation between measurable variables m/z and total intensity (I) [arb.units] of glycans; chemometrics

	Value	Error
x_c	81.86414	-
ω	6.10^6	-
A_1	15822778064.59	-
r	0.9917 ₇	

	Value	Error
x_c	85.89956	-
ω	0.00047	-
A_1	26894529293.862	-
r	0.9985 ₆	

	Value	Error
x_c	78.98008	-
ω	7.10^6	-
A_1	783008501.35179	-
r	0.9991 ₄	

Figure S17. Experimental functional relation $\{I-\langle I \rangle\}^2=f(\text{time})$ of absolute intensity of fragment ions I [arb.units] with respect to short span of scan time (a); SineSqr approximation of the latter relation examining data on glycans (2) and (8); chemometrics.

Figure S18. Mutual relation of D_{SD}^n parameters [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] of equation (2) of common ions of analytes (5), (12) and (13), respectively; chemometrics.

Figure S19. Experimental mass spectra of shown glycans; symbolic diagrams of carbohydrate fragment products.

Figure S20. Correlation between total energy (E^{TOT} [a.u.]) and optimizations step number of oxonium cation of hexose depending on the theoretical level; atom labeling scheme and chemical diagram of hexose; correlation between optimized geometry parameters of carbohydrate monomers depending on theoretical level; chemometrics.

Figure S21. Chemical diagrams of mass spectrometric species of monomeric and dimeric N-glycolylneuraminic acid (NeuGc); elemental composition of the species; theoretical m/z data and intensity ratio of the peaks of the isotope shape.

Figure S22. Chemical diagrams of mass spectrometric species; elemental composition of the species; theoretical m/z data and intensity ratio of the peaks of the isotope shape.

Figure S23. Chemical diagrams of mass spectrometric species.

Figure S24. Chemical diagrams of mass spectrometric species.

Figure S25. Chemical diagrams of mass spectrometric species.

Figure S26. Chemical diagrams of mass spectrometric species.

Figure S27. Chemical diagrams of mass spectrometric species.

Figure S28. Chemical diagrams of mass spectrometric species.

Figure S29. 2D chemical diagram of the fragment ion of glycan; symbolic diagram of the carbohydrate units of the ion (A); optimized 3D molecular structure of the species (B); relations between molecular dynamic data on potential energy [a.u.] versus time in trajectory [fs] as well as total energy (E^{TOT} [a.u.]) with respect to optimization step number of fragment ion at m/z 1187 (C).

Figure S30. 2D chemical diagram of fragment dication of glycan at m/z 848; symbolic diagram of the carbohydrate units of the ion; optimized 3D molecular structure of species depending on the position of the second charge; relation between total energy (E^{TOT} [a.u.]) with respect to the position of the charge.

Figure S31. Symbolic diagrams of the carbohydrate units of ion 1187_a and 1187_b; optimized 3D molecular structure of species; relation between total energy (E^{TOT} [a.u.]) with respect to type of carbohydrate linkage.

Figure S32. Relation between D_{QC} parameters of equation (3) depending on theoretical level of carbohydrate monomers; chemometrics; chemical diagrams of carbohydrate monomers; abbreviation of species; symbolic diagrams of the monomeric units.

Figure 33. Annotation of mass spectrometric peaks of glycan (8) according to [105]; see data on **Table S10**.

		707.34473	134711.06861	707.34467	184966.22984
		778.38165	221170.09667	778.38165	310705.34437
		849.41931	504671.2186	849.41937	717732.83216
		948.48846	333201.35761	948.48846	508302.66669
		1019.52606	143972.05765	1019.526	229680.99866

Table S2

Experimental measurable variables m/z and average total intensity I [arb.units] data on glycans (5), (12) and (13)

	(5)	(12)	(13)
291	5874	6657	4715
566	34262	46332	20991
395	20362	19438	16580

Table S3

Temporal behavior of measurable variable *intensity* of analyte fragmentation peaks (*m/z*) over short spans of scan time, *t* [mins]

Glycan (2)											
t	138	168	204	657	734	504	506	454	716		
69.601	1427	2855	1427	21841	710	5709	208	745	2131		
69.602	115611	51387	61374	1213	69984	127029	26659	248	72116		
69.604	244067	168421	351114	79478	28775	31400	18746	8777	14920		
Glycan (3)											
t	186	204	274	292	336	1172	1494	1575			
36.258	109	438	3482	1197	7118	710	366	550			
36.261	2177	14889	2394	7074	6872	237	366	1100			
36.261	26989	65686	23833	10665	60625	58471	89978	136411			
Glycan (5)											
t	292	204	138	168	274	336	186				
4.344	97	150	129	129	139	139	257				
4.344	5946	30601	26227	19542	18187	28321	8307				
4.348	97	150	129	386	139	139	129				
Glycan (6)											
t	778	707	591	491	147	162	205	849	948	1019	
12.066	2730	910	1962	1962	3446	2134	1785	4968	4968	2484	
12.068	224777	139234	480622	58852	33474	75285	220936	509178	350215	151512	
Glycan (7)											
t	778	707	849	948	1019	147	161	205			
12.104	1411	3528	7056	5015	12537	7397	7397	7397			
12.107	35278	7956	239890	5015	30088	7397	7397	7397			
12.107	324557	197556	723197	514003	238197	35503	14793	303258			
Glycan (8)											
t	138	168	204	262	274	292	308	366	407	1781	
69.601	1191	2383	3453	621	1401	621	469	8827	511	747	
69.602	114383	51234	58707	52785	35031	16146	12143	30894	52168	16813	
Glycan (9)											
t	303	331	186	204	274	292	314	366	388	565	
40.562	59	217	2453	956	1049	2098	318	956	955	384	
40.564	14727	22159	76648	237051	259150	79738	26422	26422	20692	31650	
t	657	550	476	472	256						
40.562	1310	131	393	524	0						
40.564	32352	27113	12443	5894	22398						
Glycan (10)											
t	138	204	274	366	657	695	1197				
16.311	127	179	63666	259	89	57	29				
16.313	31268	44315	32610	28728	3328	4132	6423				
16.315	127	6612	518	259	86	57	29				
Glycan (11)											
t	138	204	274	168							
16.106	96	96	67	96							
16.106	4988	4125	7303	2303							
16.109	16787	23789	14786	13333							
Glycan (12)											
t	364	411	464	522	355	380	291	274	291	395	566
4.357	9667	3625	134	10144	134	671	5102	134	4703	62364	53454
4.357	6445	10070	23900	29416	5505	4834	7116	2148	6852	20583	47310
Glycan (13)											
t	204	292	186	968							
4.277	2879	3394	58	25							
4.280	18510	4730	4335	5553							
4.281	206	1925	58	25							

Glycan (11)				
	138	204	274	168
<I>	7290.333	9336.6667	7385.333	5244
<I> ²	53148955.250889	87173345.06688889	54543143.520889	27499536
<I ² >	102230909.6667	194313787.333	90654698	61027304.667
<I ² >-<I> ²	49081954.4157777	107140442.2664	36111554.479111	33527768.6667
<(I-<I>)²>	49081941.3696	107140445.9381	36111550.255923	33527767
lnP _I	17.0532014699	17.05320658714082	17.0532040083852	17.053205154997
σ ²	2746147.1557132	6294708.673288	1775370.6762	1923297.7451
D ⁱ _{SD}	1.23576622007094.10 ⁻⁹	2.832618903.10 ⁻⁹	7.98916804.10 ⁻¹⁰	8.654839853.10 ⁻¹⁰
D ^o _{SD}	1.295174613124.10 ⁻⁹	2.827221992.10 ⁻⁹	9.529117.10 ⁻¹⁰	8.847307596.10 ⁻¹⁰
Glycan (12)				
	291	395	566	
<I>	5777.5	41473.5	50382	
<I> ²	33379506.25	1720051202.25	2538345924	
<I ² >	34534056.5	2156464192.5	2547783108	
<I ² >-<I> ²	1154550.25	436412990.25	9437184	
<(I-<I>)²>	1154550	436412990.25	9437184	
lnP _I	17.05320231	17.05320231	17.05320231	
σ ²	35541.9664	12988544.0005	290516.6551	
D ⁱ _{SD}	1.599388488.10 ⁻¹¹	5.844844.10 ⁻⁹	1.307324947.10 ⁻¹⁰	
D ^o _{SD}	3.04662719.10 ⁻¹¹	1.151606599.10 ⁻⁸	2.49028411.10 ⁻¹⁰	
	364	411	464	522
<I>	8056	6847.5	12017	19780
<I> ²	64899136	46888256.25	144408289	391248400
<I ² >	67494457	57272762.5	285613978	484100896
<I ² >-<I> ²	2595321	10384506.25	141205689	92852496
D ^o _{SD}	6.848533054.10 ⁻¹¹	2.74026350.10 ⁻¹⁰	3.7261357213.10 ⁻⁹	2.4501916644.10 ⁻⁹
	355	380	291	274
<I>	2819.5	2752.5	6109	1141
<I> ²	7949580.25	7576256.25	37319881	1301881
<I ² >	15161490.5	11908898.5	38333930	2315930
<I ² >-<I> ²	7211910.25	4332642.25	1014049	1014049
D ^o _{SD}	1.903078876.10 ⁻¹⁰	1.143297636.10 ⁻¹⁰	2.67587250.10 ⁻¹¹	2.6758725.10 ⁻¹¹
Glycan (13)				
	292	186	204	968
<I>	3349.667	1483.667	7198.333	1867.667
<I> ²	11220269.010889	2201266.778	51815997.978889	3488180.022889
<I ² >	12532587	6266317.6667	116983725.667	10279019.6667
<I ² >-<I> ²	1312317.989111	4065050.887	65167727.6878	6790839.6438
<(I-<I>)²>	1312320.49193	4065053.9259	65167766.66	6790839.777
lnP _I	17.053206	17.05321875	17.053216	17.053206
σ ²	582170.6821	309335.5013	4086873.19826	1593313.24836
D ⁱ _{SD}	2.67798513.10 ⁻¹⁰	1.39200975.10 ⁻¹⁰	1.83909.10 ⁻⁹	2.10221.10 ⁻¹¹
D ^o _{SD}	3.46294470.10 ⁻¹¹	1.072685629.10 ⁻¹⁰	1.71964599822.10 ⁻⁹	1.791966.10 ⁻¹⁰

N	-2.38043	0.66943	-0.56962	N	-2.369846	0.632593	-0.58495
C	-1.22537	-1.16153	0.85788	C	-1.214981	-1.198162	0.842506
O	-2.35157	-2.06402	0.9562	O	-2.341222	-2.100554	0.940957
C	-3.73897	0.24367	-0.32293	C	-3.728534	0.207117	-0.338158
O	3.4673	-1.77044	-0.63062	O	3.47765	-1.806986	-0.645846
O	2.62225	-3.40777	0.83278	O	2.632567	-3.444286	0.817542
C	1.77009	2.0267	-0.44498	C	1.780423	1.990139	-0.460247
C	-4.6075	0.92184	0.437	C	-4.597156	0.885306	0.421766
O	-4.00496	-0.91654	-1.06434	O	-3.994604	-0.953081	-1.079583
O	2.72583	0.92131	-0.66929	O	2.736176	0.884753	-0.684527
C	2.33643	3.07837	0.56045	C	2.346776	3.041827	0.54522
O	1.22945	4.0142	0.73393	O	1.239807	3.977663	0.718692
H	2.05029	-0.0362	-0.95097	H	2.060975	-0.072159	-0.966339
H	-0.13326	0.74424	-1.88982	H	-0.122791	0.706452	-1.901884
H	-1.61863	-1.16732	-1.27422	H	-1.608464	-1.20721	-1.29304
H	0.83219	0.77597	1.05468	H	0.842666	0.739613	1.03961
H	0.00253	3.13755	0.6981	H	0.012911	3.101029	0.682869
H	0.28572	-2.68743	1.6421	H	0.296606	-2.723903	1.626545
H	-2.06215	1.47058	0.03362	H	-2.051307	1.433394	0.018564
H	-1.21459	-0.41409	1.68309	H	-1.204415	-0.450161	1.667237
H	-2.29856	-2.38236	1.92142	H	-2.2882	-2.418849	1.906185
H	3.59203	-3.70035	0.74129	H	3.602397	-3.736805	0.726012
H	1.52844	2.51868	-1.4084	H	1.538803	2.482146	-1.423669
H	-5.64988	0.62064	0.50535	H	-5.639515	0.584134	0.490067
H	-4.30181	1.80977	0.98254	H	-4.291456	1.773193	0.967316
H	-4.9641	-1.13193	-0.81862	H	-4.95373	-1.168481	-0.833869
H	3.38439	1.18498	-1.38602	H	3.394752	1.148407	-1.401265
H	3.23647	3.5801	0.15268	H	3.246826	3.543542	0.137415
H	2.6093	2.57015	1.50614	H	2.619655	2.533612	1.490902
H	1.456	4.53723	1.56963	H	1.466354	4.500698	1.554399

488 (TS)

488 (GS)

■-2-AB

■-2-AB

	x	y	z		x	y	z
C	1.12172	-2.20321	0.1544	C	1.113311	-2.2075	0.154782
C	2.62829	-1.9089	-0.39062	C	2.603861	-1.950562	-0.342162
C	0.04627	-1.9139	-0.88674	C	0.005823	-1.886123	-0.918397
O	0.96632	-3.53915	0.51207	O	1.009546	-3.605009	0.47291
O	3.32425	-2.98214	0.30247	O	3.321202	-2.997093	0.318902
C	3.15976	-0.49554	-0.00136	C	3.156703	-0.510501	0.015064
C	-1.3103	-2.59304	-0.49139	C	-1.313352	-2.607987	-0.474972
O	-0.25658	-0.45327	-1.08275	O	-0.259645	-0.468199	-1.066334
C	2.98534	0.49396	-1.20422	C	2.982288	0.479003	-1.187799
N	4.59979	-0.50491	0.38509	N	4.596734	-0.519864	0.401509
N	1.59647	1.13624	-1.2415	N	1.593416	1.121288	-1.225074
O	-1.76334	-2.0482	0.79193	O	-1.766393	-2.063152	0.808349
C	-2.86406	-1.15389	0.62474	C	-2.867112	-1.168847	0.641167
O	-2.48233	-0.15049	-0.39638	O	-2.485376	-0.165443	-0.379964
C	-4.25501	-1.77439	0.18835	C	-4.25806	-1.78934	0.204773
C	5.64404	-1.2964	-0.1319	C	5.640988	-1.311347	-0.115474
C	-3.23792	1.09927	-0.25919	C	-3.240968	1.084315	-0.242764
C	-5.03536	-0.69296	-0.66091	C	-5.038414	-0.707915	-0.644484
O	-5.03857	-2.0601	1.36313	O	-5.04162	-2.075053	1.379551
C	-4.75875	0.73581	-0.08035	C	-4.761806	0.720861	-0.063931
C	-2.97854	1.93687	-1.53032	C	-2.981594	1.921919	-1.513897
O	-6.45907	-0.88983	-0.41891	O	-6.462125	-0.904778	-0.402486
O	-5.5746	1.722	-0.74859	O	-5.577649	1.70705	-0.73217
C	7.04629	-0.6886	0.11125	C	7.043238	-0.703549	0.127666

C	1.32945	1.761553	-0.775411	C	1.31726	1.77203	-0.7766
C	0.340604	2.971005	-0.853364	C	0.32842	2.98148	-0.85455
C	0.746845	0.645404	0.142438	C	0.73466	0.65588	0.14125
O	-0.597985	0.36902	-0.341748	O	-0.61017	0.37949	-0.34293
O	-0.544946	2.969178	0.324884	O	-0.55713	2.97965	0.3237
C	-3.915153	0.009233	-0.207554	C	-3.92734	0.01971	-0.20874
C	6.078043	-0.273712	-0.845589	C	6.06586	-0.26324	-0.84677
O	5.863766	-2.58105	0.019857	O	5.85158	-2.57058	0.01867
C	-4.188677	-2.5507	-0.616711	C	-4.20086	-2.54023	-0.6179
O	-2.056801	-1.40153	-0.310043	O	-2.06899	-1.39106	-0.31123
C	-3.226203	1.060023	0.781197	C	-3.23839	1.0705	0.78001
O	-3.234032	0.281142	-1.478174	O	-3.24622	0.29162	-1.47936
O	-2.702907	2.041989	-0.155385	O	-2.71509	2.05246	-0.15657
C	-1.239435	-0.552783	0.586539	C	-1.25162	-0.54231	0.58535
C	-2.094328	0.334213	1.598627	C	-2.10651	0.34469	1.59744
O	-2.754999	-0.413137	2.647985	O	-2.76718	-0.40266	2.6468
O	-4.061098	-2.20764	-2.019469	O	-4.07328	-2.19717	-2.02066
H	1.48725	-1.159997	-0.843075	H	1.47506	-1.14952	-0.84427
H	3.564392	-2.036174	0.726616	H	3.5522	-2.02573	0.72544
H	4.500191	1.564454	0.163758	H	4.48798	1.57493	0.16258
H	1.80907	-1.041145	1.98309	H	1.79689	-1.03067	1.9819
H	-3.494715	-1.577586	1.274014	H	-3.5069	-1.56711	1.27283
H	1.468532	1.348035	-1.795986	H	1.45635	1.35851	-1.79717
H	-0.275054	2.9059	-1.770312	H	-0.28724	2.91637	-1.7715
H	0.928517	3.906163	-0.875549	H	0.91633	3.91664	-0.87673
H	0.725236	1.034154	1.181364	H	0.71305	1.04463	1.18018
H	-0.717217	3.941036	0.534388	H	-0.7294	3.95151	0.5332
H	-5.005954	0.144337	-0.297371	H	-5.01814	0.15481	-0.29856
H	5.399955	0.207456	-1.558529	H	5.38777	0.21793	-1.55972
H	6.949335	-0.668396	-1.378846	H	6.93715	-0.65792	-1.38003
H	6.419639	0.471324	-0.117238	H	6.40745	0.4818	-0.11842
H	-5.241747	-2.579592	-0.267434	H	-5.25393	-2.56912	-0.26862
H	-3.7187	-3.522493	-0.363143	H	-3.73089	-3.51202	-0.36433
H	-2.473726	-0.464307	-1.345495	H	-2.48591	-0.45383	-1.34668
H	-3.95624	1.51389	1.477064	H	-3.96843	1.52436	1.47588
H	-2.79126	1.335856	-1.086287	H	-2.80345	1.34633	-1.08747
H	-1.695492	2.391466	0.089753	H	-1.70768	2.40194	0.08857
H	-0.474088	-1.192428	1.100265	H	-0.48627	-1.18196	1.09908
H	-1.39791	1.098978	2.002106	H	-1.4101	1.10945	2.00092
H	-1.980459	-0.750873	3.212098	H	-1.99264	-0.7404	3.21091
H	-4.482619	-3.007719	-2.47963	H	-4.4948	-2.99725	-2.48082

292_a (TS)

	x	y	z
C	0.19052	0.33469	1.24555
C	1.65201	-0.19697	0.9001
O	-0.77971	-0.76917	1.31975
C	-0.41192	1.30795	0.13038
N	2.37017	0.7489	0.05999
C	3.59767	0.34867	-0.622

292_a (GS)

	x	y	z
C	0.163094	0.306344	1.237676
C	1.610832	-0.25737	0.933447
O	-0.830343	-0.774919	1.289904
C	-0.388982	1.220074	0.081294
N	2.347313	0.711389	0.06587
C	3.574812	0.311166	-0.616125

H	1.047858	2.94347	-0.253093	H	1.062266	2.940185	-0.242005
H	-0.222214	-1.432666	1.984705	H	-0.228709	-1.434923	1.98583
H	-0.000604	-3.697934	1.823643	H	-0.017615	-3.700836	1.819831
H	5.353707	-1.462168	0.218886	H	5.347473	-1.486482	0.221384
H	-5.299057	-1.482576	-0.839671	H	-5.304983	-1.454986	-0.839973
H	-4.628468	0.13423	-0.497872	H	-4.62697	0.157926	-0.494443
H	-4.754364	-1.068784	0.811099	H	-4.758814	-1.047365	0.811844
H	-1.503546	2.234419	-0.9355	H	-1.492222	2.244526	-0.926638
H	-1.598417	4.432476	0.300639	H	-1.577169	4.440254	0.314307
H	-0.466901	3.781109	1.55114	H	-0.449028	3.780887	1.563666
H	-3.08095	2.222566	0.70574	H	-3.07007	2.236387	0.714158
H	0.797179	4.835879	-0.068845	H	0.820381	4.833318	-0.053668

274_b (TS)

274_b (GS)

◆

x y z

C	-0.03845	-0.35841	1.2698
C	1.46394	-0.16052	0.81169
O	-0.39894	-1.78099	1.21228
C	-1.0427	0.3717	0.28073
N	1.54339	1.04435	-0.05143
C	2.81396	1.40159	-0.65702
O	-2.16198	-0.53733	-0.04888
C	-0.34905	-2.04418	-0.19791
C	0.81955	-1.95244	-0.83581
C	-1.72729	-1.79925	-0.78157
C	1.98406	-1.46229	0.05795
O	2.33412	-2.39554	1.11185
O	-2.51459	-2.27505	-1.58613
C	2.88705	2.91779	-0.99664
O	3.68676	0.56672	-0.93941
C	-1.65431	1.69492	0.84657
C	-2.74341	2.2394	-0.15963
O	-0.53419	2.60165	0.94558
O	-3.7118	1.1452	-0.37083
H	-0.19484	-0.01348	2.31804
H	2.09247	-0.07205	1.72729
H	-0.45751	0.61921	-0.64807
H	1.05263	1.86416	0.39366
H	-3.03367	0.13974	-0.3305
H	0.93056	-2.04495	-1.91336
H	2.85396	-1.12768	-0.5524
H	2.87359	-3.10648	0.6283
H	3.79905	3.11022	-1.56468
H	2.94092	3.5012	-0.04963
H	2.02119	3.22152	-1.54234
H	-2.1403	1.49114	1.83099
H	-3.25993	3.11902	0.2678
H	-2.24499	2.52132	-1.10927
H	-0.81967	3.29495	1.6355
H	-4.20977	1.33052	-1.21761

◆

x y z

C	0.045965	-0.421563	-1.268495
C	-1.457157	-0.220728	-0.814633
O	0.402792	-1.843105	-1.212984
C	1.045032	0.312193	-0.281371
N	-1.536817	0.986335	0.051757
C	-2.805494	1.341443	0.656917
O	2.16418	-0.599796	0.049263
C	0.359319	-2.105622	0.194889
C	-0.813118	-2.015374	0.838489
C	1.737373	-1.860548	0.7793
C	-1.973885	-1.523492	-0.061131
O	-2.326037	-2.455354	-1.114875
O	2.520162	-2.334178	1.583369
C	-2.883807	2.85385	0.991164
O	-3.680368	0.508467	0.938921
C	1.66191	1.633847	-0.84717
C	2.750373	2.179967	0.157433
O	0.539803	2.542623	-0.951297
O	3.716558	1.085251	0.371302
H	0.200632	-0.08576	-2.309723
H	-2.081141	-0.133414	-1.725671
H	0.482363	0.555682	0.643008
H	-1.038325	1.796179	-0.395473
H	3.057111	0.073433	0.329372
H	-0.919626	-2.114478	1.925274
H	-2.838359	-1.191364	0.554554
H	-2.849277	-3.167697	-0.61231
H	-3.783292	3.04701	1.584608
H	-2.931449	3.443263	0.067211
H	-1.999125	3.162403	1.560275
H	2.151604	1.426695	-1.820963
H	3.285163	3.054537	-0.257811
H	2.270404	2.460795	1.1149
H	0.837202	3.233126	-1.630218
H	4.218047	1.260134	1.228743

274_a (GS)			274_a (TS)				
	x	y	z		x	y	z
C	-0.150156	-0.139864	-1.255735	C	0.18044	-0.11529	1.25173
C	-1.197341	-0.755413	-0.257367	C	1.24022	-0.70146	0.21558
O	1.005152	-1.017091	-1.583562	O	-0.9536	-1.01324	1.5997
C	0.542102	1.196278	-0.798377	C	-0.55799	1.27542	0.83215
N	-2.034826	0.3351	0.292546	N	2.06092	0.36807	-0.30915
C	-3.415908	0.253029	-0.157644	C	3.442	0.28599	0.14104
O	-0.418903	2.234576	-0.522009	O	0.44499	2.26754	0.50541
C	1.517835	-1.489022	-0.370686	C	-1.49175	-1.45606	0.35409
C	0.65087	-2.48632	0.406353	C	-0.62478	-2.45336	-0.42295
C	3.005382	-1.18686	-0.266413	C	-2.97929	-1.1539	0.24982
C	-0.601706	-1.644424	0.903446	C	0.62779	-1.61146	-0.92005
O	-1.684311	-2.505687	1.30196	O	1.7104	-2.47272	-1.31856
O	4.197672	-1.107508	-0.3965	O	-4.17158	-1.07455	0.3799
C	-4.224803	1.526041	0.183372	C	4.25089	1.559	-0.19997
O	-3.852901	-0.768716	-0.705175	O	3.87899	-0.73575	0.68858
C	1.385342	0.978915	0.5186	C	-1.35926	1.01188	-0.53519
C	2.391388	2.155955	0.697054	C	-2.3653	2.18892	-0.71366
O	2.024177	-0.373595	0.628373	O	-1.99809	-0.34063	-0.64497
O	1.48573	3.300029	0.745334	O	-1.45964	3.33299	-0.76193
H	-0.646166	0.048116	-2.226269	H	0.67229	0.08108	2.20972
H	-1.890582	-1.414005	-0.820775	H	1.91665	-1.381	0.80413
H	1.247006	1.479974	-1.610242	H	-1.22115	1.51306	1.59391
H	-1.577252	1.282945	0.146297	H	1.60334	1.3159	-0.1629
H	0.187497	2.92051	-0.033929	H	-0.1614	2.95349	0.01732
H	1.204406	-2.930652	1.244857	H	-1.17832	-2.89769	-1.26146
H	0.325956	-3.274072	-0.290438	H	-0.29987	-3.24111	0.27384
H	-0.254797	-0.990894	1.729471	H	0.28088	-0.95794	-1.74608
H	-1.384531	-2.852399	2.210053	H	1.41062	-2.81944	-2.22665
H	-5.25587	1.408157	-0.165258	H	5.28196	1.44112	0.14866
H	-3.776901	2.402281	-0.300696	H	3.80299	2.43524	0.2841
H	-4.22472	1.686951	1.267919	H	4.25081	1.71991	-1.28452
H	0.685568	0.980283	1.380056	H	-0.65946	1.01325	-1.39663
H	2.976317	2.047019	1.632362	H	-2.95023	2.07999	-1.64896
H	3.087443	2.203838	-0.163995	H	-3.06136	2.2368	0.14739
H	2.06946	4.11029	0.589788	H	-2.04337	4.14325	-0.60639

472_α _{2,6} (TS)			472_α _{2,6} (GS)				
	x	y	z		x	y	z
C	2.4296	0.24148	-0.82507	C	0.00000000	0.00000000	0.00000000
C	2.01302	1.5208	-0.04557	C	1.55383979	0.00000000	0.00000000
O	1.3046	-0.66316	-1.11914	O	-0.55423145	1.37528156	0.00000000
C	3.57002	-0.53687	-0.15603	C	-0.67575060	-0.87660004	1.14154273
N	3.16186	2.3337	0.28208	N	2.05830012	-1.37903801	0.00745741
C	3.75243	3.06351	-0.80247	C	1.90365054	-2.15163363	-1.19121662
O	3.92036	-0.20249	1.13912	O	0.27077154	-1.30871189	2.13862703
C	0.13647	-0.77249	-0.22829	C	0.13969057	2.48377057	0.68525155
C	0.01195	0.28693	0.92912	C	1.63672313	2.24566002	1.10911301

C 0.08607 -2.27633 0.38326
C 1.34191 0.99927 1.30949
O 1.14723 2.08271 2.24601
O 0.66018 -3.34934 0.01305
O -0.86216 -2.34508 1.36673
C 4.71892 4.17477 -0.32332
O 3.51599 2.75307 -1.98106
C 3.32251 -2.14861 -0.18303
C 4.68207 -2.90608 -0.10858
O 2.47966 -2.61741 -1.29965
O 5.30439 -2.3668 1.09484
O -6.44883 -0.93636 -1.00378
C -5.46272 0.10584 -0.87662
C -5.02624 -0.00788 0.62727
C -4.01899 1.14001 0.98608
C -3.29921 1.62083 -0.33179
C -3.12148 0.40661 -1.30991
C -2.26803 -0.71691 -0.5999
O -6.20121 0.06043 1.46394
O -2.96207 0.68727 1.8768
O -1.96892 2.14337 -0.06122
O -4.37891 -0.11425 -1.83388
O -0.93121 -0.70819 -1.20676
H 2.75124 0.61874 -1.83368
H 1.24487 2.04088 -0.62836
H 1.87343 -1.70305 -1.46864
H 4.48301 -0.4335 -0.89519
H 3.11699 2.77371 1.2242
H 4.64211 -0.90785 1.3521
H -0.41277 -0.22047 1.80343
H -0.72946 1.04039 0.5728
H 2.07772 0.31141 1.77291
H 0.4602 2.66203 1.76664
H -0.90951 -3.33354 1.61268
H 5.48577 3.74738 0.33346
H 4.16827 4.94135 0.23524
H 5.19911 4.63843 -1.19091
H 2.78313 -2.34607 0.76468
H 4.51992 -4.00018 -0.0377
H 5.27288 -2.69606 -1.02085
H 1.67692 -3.16013 -0.77864
H 6.28541 -2.5929 0.99914
H -6.90414 -0.73714 -1.88735
H -5.91654 1.11337 -1.05047
H -4.49828 -0.97972 0.73785
H -4.59495 1.97973 1.42765
H -3.93088 2.38582 -0.82725
H -2.53544 0.74448 -2.18798
H -2.2554 -0.52282 0.4899
H -2.7409 -1.69883 -0.79621
H -6.84025 -0.50326 0.90051

C -0.72651630 2.99791900 1.95938138
C 2.03973785 0.75202350 1.27502838
O 3.45833706 0.57665670 1.48862928
O -1.94175661 2.80034229 2.27900759
O 0.00334487 3.90172633 2.68155655
C2.77950940-3.42888809 -1.20022311
O1.09552680-1.80846546 -2.06902095
C-1.82327330-0.10153156 1.91392430
C-2.76803193-1.15169616 2.57140265
O-2.55696246 0.86579349 1.07549198
O-1.87059675-1.93378527 3.41358918
O1.42573152 8.79344644 -0.90489865
C 2.05413604 7.52562296 -1.17414350
C 2.63949772 7.12164689 0.22560319
C 3.46955104 5.79621996 0.10229096
C 2.95582845 4.98414929 -1.14777957
C 1.41511848 5.21779375 -1.33286889
C 0.65478695 4.75256281 -0.02893089
O 3.46424144 8.19952143 0.71877218
O 3.28585398 4.92214939 1.25020101
O3.14848891 3.55232006 -0.97851746
O1.06917053 6.58442106 -1.70651261
O-0.031311913.49278623 -0.34145517
H-0.32349604-0.40893024 0.97849715
H1.87316196 0.54736271 -0.91120758
H-1.74584149 1.15355068 0.37442880
H-1.14967546-1.73380788 0.61836830
H 2.92289395-1.49247606 0.57563789
H-0.38161870-1.77306828 2.78870821
H 1.81196714 2.79410729 2.04225821
H 2.25712027 2.71587936 0.31014221
H 1.53023914 0.26444767 2.13059886
H 3.85888500 1.05268705 0.68217944
H-0.64480293 4.25587531 3.38459798
H2.57258567-4.03188353 -0.30822013
H3.84269435-3.15963406 -1.20099703
H2.55739790-4.01617336 -2.09690190
H -1.328967990.45603704 2.73419439
H-3.56176938-0.65214847 3.16198809
H-3.24771952-1.76264144 1.78270360
H -2.492433611.79004636 1.66880359
H-2.37487272-2.79061212 3.59864764
H 1.243096309.17736215 -1.82519193
H 2.894969517.63937989 -1.90308724
H 1.77310688 6.92736648 0.89424405
H 4.536293936.06831271 -0.03867312
H 3.48118985 5.34908393 -2.0536041
H 1.057302524.57022443 -2.15822895
H 1.38476691 4.66005595 0.79814839
H -0.104531335.51581895 0.23028750
H 2.89134237 8.99407122 0.42883901

H	-3.48505004	0.38520999	2.69291926	H	3.62199416	5.49964724	2.01460004
H	-2.15610222	2.85970303	0.63334694	H	4.142630073	4.9049821	-0.78241867
204_a (TS)				204_a (GS)			
	x	y	z		x	y	z
C	-1.039551	0.897877	0.763294	C	-1.03292	0.869277	0.803412
C	-0.02018	1.630214	-0.178817	C	-0.037137	1.595582	-0.161029
N	-2.330815	0.639975	0.049446	N	-2.35112	0.639039	0.130127
C	-0.657519	-0.581552	1.191362	C	-0.63712	-0.628746	1.152473
O	-0.186919	3.039534	0.092754	O	-0.130567	3.018079	0.046594
O	0.668361	-1.015716	1.127687	O	0.689155	-1.063014	1.055153
C	-2.490399	-0.66715	-0.244526	C	-2.507019	-0.650422	-0.234452
C	1.369176	-0.480316	-0.053063	C	1.395921	-0.482996	-0.103762
C	2.777219	-1.135572	-0.068474	C	2.805605	-1.137675	-0.109459
C	1.440373	1.081995	0.06692	C	1.417025	1.076566	0.086058
O	2.3341	1.589927	-0.954595	O	2.186079	1.832369	-0.875974
O	2.591996	-2.501854	-0.513127	O	2.607489	-2.521579	-0.489075
C	-3.60894	-1.243838	-1.102348	C	-3.650088	-1.191907	-1.082734
O	-1.556072	-1.460214	0.282921	O	-1.547474	-1.462468	0.215785
H	-1.222161	1.518587	1.659643	H	-1.17495	1.457825	1.727897
H	-0.274002	1.371585	-1.22999	H	-0.301574	1.304445	-1.202364
H	-2.932007	1.399273	-0.341115	H	-2.965935	1.413795	-0.205645
H	-1.033454	-0.806366	2.216397	H	-0.996971	-0.904124	2.171047
H	0.436609	3.462905	-0.589544	H	0.725549	3.31427	-0.421976
H	0.834343	-0.768713	-0.980175	H	0.875773	-0.75069	-1.045062
H	3.207907	-1.062409	0.951321	H	3.253119	-1.020829	0.89918
H	3.403547	-0.527109	-0.753756	H	3.43568	-0.579377	-0.833209
H	1.761829	1.336786	1.09582	H	1.717252	1.28701	1.133563
H	2.782623	2.377375	-0.4975	H	3.143199	1.728617	-0.555806
H	3.538628	-2.869164	-0.481979	H	3.551883	-2.894369	-0.450521
H	-4.57821	-0.876335	-0.735461	H	-4.606857	-0.967713	-0.587987
H	-3.469775	-0.920354	-2.145193	H	-3.631879	-0.710007	-2.07157
H	-3.572979	-2.339251	-1.045799	H	-3.529503	-2.277297	-1.191358
204_b (GS)				204_b (TS)			
	x	y	z		x	y	z
C	-0.796145	0.208671	0.012426	C	-0.7963	0.21379	0.01197
C	0.080998	1.499877	-0.04224	C	0.08886	1.5237	-0.06675
N	-2.182071	0.432385	-0.162442	N	-2.16758	0.42305	-0.14865
C	-0.306434	-1.021577	0.248702	C	-0.33599	-0.98172	0.27231
O	-0.201851	2.402337	1.056282	O	-0.20468	2.4128	1.0478
O	1.114873	-1.146987	0.45504	O	1.11204	-1.13653	0.44656
C	-3.187643	-0.615378	-0.107416	C	-3.19047	-0.60492	-0.11589
C	1.8906	-0.24065	-0.404764	C	1.88777	-0.23019	-0.41324
C	3.323447	-0.855034	-0.222442	C	3.32062	-0.84457	-0.23092
C	1.632914	1.206673	0.09116	C	1.63009	1.21713	0.08268
O	2.454629	2.081161	-0.710101	O	2.4518	2.09162	-0.71858
O	2.983101	-2.282556	0.015772	O	2.98027	-2.2721	0.00729
C	-4.60069	-0.074498	-0.423479	C	-4.60352	-0.06404	-0.43196
O	-2.893427	-1.782927	0.179877	O	-2.89626	-1.77247	0.1714

H	-0.093609	1.976554	-1.033833	H	-0.09644	1.98703	-1.04234
H	-2.470445	1.345992	-0.562502	H	-2.47325	1.35639	-0.57095
H	-0.903217	-1.934846	0.344106	H	-0.90604	-1.92437	0.33563
H	-1.191656	2.607035	0.944608	H	-1.19449	2.61749	0.93613
H	1.841433	-2.06571	0.349009	H	1.8386	-2.05525	0.34053
H	1.552158	-0.357208	-1.454226	H	1.54933	-0.34675	-1.4627
H	3.849545	-0.428406	0.651216	H	3.84672	-0.41795	0.64274
H	3.941927	-0.762011	-1.133097	H	3.9391	-0.75155	-1.14158
H	1.871431	1.253924	1.17625	H	1.8686	1.26438	1.16777
H	2.255913	2.990399	-0.303079	H	2.25308	3.00086	-0.31156
H	3.563085	-2.626801	0.767679	H	3.56026	-2.61634	0.7592
H	-4.870261	0.714529	0.289344	H	-4.87309	0.72499	0.28087
H	-4.631098	0.338037	-1.439607	H	-4.63393	0.3485	-1.44809
H	-5.321586	-0.894896	-0.34541	H	-5.32441	-0.88444	-0.35389

366_bg_b (GS)

366_bg_b (TS)

	x	y	z		x	y	z
C	0	0	0	C	-3.66022	-1.11727	-0.48414
C	1.35003612	0	0	C	-2.87045	0.01708	-0.67515
C	2.10797539	1.36748642	0	C	-1.37454	-0.22513	-1.06895
C	1.51739182	2.1825684	-1.21733154	C	-0.8216	-1.17602	-0.06643
C	-0.04940438	2.28598634	-1.08050684	C	-1.6275	-2.55604	-0.12466
C	-0.7768581	1.87466021	-2.39893168	C	-1.96997	-3.0208	1.32562
C	1.9504536	-2.38795203	-0.24108997	C	-4.30217	1.83527	0.21033
C	3.19527015	-3.28774651	-0.40019292	C	-4.22966	3.35236	0.48904
N	2.29071332	-0.98422394	-0.10652688	N	-3.07367	1.31348	-0.35791
O	3.49080548	1.01669816	-0.10775691	O	-0.85576	1.13451	-1.05985
O	2.01431703	3.54929828	-1.27484378	O	0.57845	-1.62405	-0.52187
O	-0.58654031	1.3626009	-0.00595682	O	-2.95829	-2.36961	-0.82471
O	0.0359037	2.41935893	-3.46897414	O	-0.77204	-2.76448	2.10122
O	0.76604911	-2.74924642	-0.21805993	O	-5.26401	1.08315	0.4178
C	3.1287022	3.60217661	-2.1859585	C	1.52639	-0.82564	0.21212
C	3.53548236	5.10687405	-2.36970321	C	2.96409	-1.37838	-0.08926
C	4.8778915	5.20312325	-3.1727374	C	4.04397	-0.41059	0.50524
C	5.94430459	4.25211707	-2.53913573	C	3.74123	1.05772	0.06309
C	5.37197618	2.78856455	-2.50291204	C	2.28361	1.43981	0.51056
C	6.36953166	1.75001211	-1.9168312	C	1.88849	2.89867	0.14614
O	3.73773109	5.74794626	-1.09265036	O	3.19338	-1.47639	-1.51073
O	5.28724325	6.58059627	-2.9795606	O	5.2747	-0.85617	-0.11854
O	7.13412213	4.44687337	-3.33700649	O	4.80744	1.84514	0.64048
O	4.21696987	2.79890453	-1.60612688	O	1.36497	0.57071	-0.2237
O	5.62074311	0.51387173	-1.78076426	O	0.47414	3.0146	0.45179
H	-0.7525179	-0.78629532	-0.04018581	H	-4.68618	-1.26798	-0.15589
H	1.89939548	1.93013318	0.93589665	H	-1.37735	-0.59774	-2.14747
H	1.72798738	1.63093587	-2.15425617	H	-0.79286	-0.82401	0.89838
H	-0.32867736	3.30354395	-0.74285792	H	-1.1092	-3.34142	-0.70945
H	-1.81193004	2.26903644	-2.3844268	H	-2.26599	-4.08811	1.30785
H	-0.82620062	0.76427863	-2.41928674	H	-2.84114	-2.42219	1.6699
H	3.82875124	-3.20794875	0.4916541	H	-4.06867	3.89608	-0.44985
H	3.77688796	-2.97236808	-1.27477013	H	-3.39719	3.56954	1.16908
H	2.87687136	-4.32755813	-0.52865948	H	-5.1692	3.68254	0.94438

H	3.22741785	-0.37939893	-0.18646796	H	-2.05081	1.71909	-0.55511
H	3.90804506	1.68128366	-0.81902341	H	0.10129	1.0305	-0.61839
H	-0.47771489	1.8079111	0.89981726	H	-2.82267	-2.46185	-1.82655
H	-0.52324366	2.20722667	-4.2886794	H	-1.01288	-3.16541	3.00167
H	2.86447529	3.1646911	-3.1824229	H	1.33445	-0.87181	1.31447
H	2.72498293	5.58210642	-2.96452242	H	3.03834	-2.36108	0.42586
H	4.73941674	4.93882264	-4.241045	H	4.0777	-0.46051	1.6128
H	6.08637614	4.56066786	-1.48190575	H	3.74666	1.08411	-1.04704
H	5.05995363	2.46978501	-3.51862586	H	2.1607	1.28471	1.60212
H	6.74821611	2.12318412	-0.94323651	H	2.10361	3.07302	-0.92804
H	7.22879444	1.65966916	-2.61165673	H	2.51688	3.59057	0.74252
H	4.38480699	6.48187503	-1.4017489	H	4.21653	-1.39987	-1.49633
H	6.28148653	6.53229777	-3.1855943	H	5.8684	-0.03774	-0.01378
H	7.8700928	4.04144114	-2.76673499	H	4.75107	2.72496	0.13651
H	6.30848086	-0.11306556	-1.37506242	H	0.26934	3.96914	0.17334

366_bg_a (TS)

366_bg_a (GS)

	x	y	z
C	-3.81506	-0.09797	-0.89583
C	-2.85861	-1.26581	-0.47491
C	-1.35853	-0.93486	-0.08815
C	-0.95899	0.52632	-0.64528
C	-2.10103	1.54538	-0.63399
C	-1.70915	2.8824	-1.34418
C	-4.49284	-0.83747	1.19358
C	-5.28627	-0.9281	2.49031
N	-3.59719	-1.74602	0.76311
O	-0.58607	-1.99911	-0.60058
O	0.08665	1.03194	0.22198
O	-3.27037	1.08757	-1.40515
O	-0.40933	3.30833	-0.86321
O	-4.65674	0.19885	0.36566
C	1.3979	0.69073	-0.25526
C	2.42318	1.52215	0.59608
C	3.88344	1.05551	0.28084
C	3.96024	-0.49901	0.39634
C	2.90415	-1.13846	-0.57629
C	2.94755	-2.69223	-0.58068
O	2.20072	1.32853	2.01077
O	4.68163	1.65046	1.33689
O	5.34871	-0.81829	0.14309
O	1.57514	-0.76224	-0.09612
O	1.86324	-3.12149	-1.44391
H	4.57346	-0.44391	-1.64269
H	-2.87336	-2.07453	-1.2266
H	-1.33022	-0.79236	0.99937
H	-0.58037	0.3895	-1.71567
H	-2.38042	1.73301	0.42194
H	-2.50883	3.62244	-1.14127
H	-1.71179	2.68112	-2.43631
H	-5.78132	0.03404	2.67304
H	-4.61127	-1.17387	3.32186
H	-6.04505	-1.71967	2.39166
H	-3.28669	-2.56499	1.33184
H	0.37915	-1.64166	-0.46337

	x	y	z
C	-3.82224000	-0.08385700	-0.90659400
C	-2.87266500	-1.26773500	-0.46505700
C	-1.37946100	-0.90700300	-0.11265800
C	-0.94097000	0.51064900	-0.67666200
C	-2.10591700	1.55490800	-0.63788200
C	-1.71404000	2.89193400	-1.34807700
C	-4.49773000	-0.82794000	1.18968500
C	-5.29115900	-0.91856600	2.48642000
N	-3.60208400	-1.73649100	0.75922300
O	-0.59096000	-1.98957800	-0.60447500
O	0.08175500	1.04147100	0.21808400
O	-3.27526500	1.09709900	-1.40904700
O	-0.41422800	3.31785900	-0.86710400
O	-4.66163300	0.20838000	0.36176700
C	1.39300600	0.70025700	-0.25915100
C	2.41828600	1.53168000	0.59218400
C	3.87854600	1.06504200	0.27694900
C	3.95534400	-0.48948000	0.39245000
C	2.89926000	-1.12892500	-0.58018200
C	2.94265400	-2.68269400	-0.58457600
O	2.19582500	1.33806600	2.00687600
O	4.67673900	1.65999000	1.33299300
O	5.34381300	-0.80876100	0.13919300
O	1.57024300	-0.75270400	-0.10001300
O	1.85835100	-3.11195900	-1.44780700
H	-4.57835500	-0.43437900	-1.64658300
H	-2.87825200	-2.06500000	-1.23048800
H	-1.33511300	-0.78282500	0.99545100
H	-0.58524300	0.39902900	-1.71960800
H	-2.38531300	1.74253800	0.41804400
H	-2.51372600	3.63196900	-1.14516200
H	-1.71668200	2.69064800	-2.44020000
H	-5.78621400	0.04356900	2.66915100
H	-4.61616700	-1.16433900	3.31796600
H	-6.04993900	-1.71013400	2.38776500
H	-3.29158300	-2.55545900	1.32794400
H	0.37425500	-1.63213100	-0.46726500

C	2.33099	-1.04664	-0.45197	C	2.342807	-1.047132	-0.456151
C	-1.21086	1.61836	-0.73038	C	-1.199089	1.617883	-0.734514
N	3.60971	-0.48347	-0.91482	N	3.621475	-0.483922	-0.91903
O	-1.54145	1.82515	0.71841	O	-1.529608	1.824704	0.714231
C	-1.18533	0.06999	-1.03769	C	-1.173468	0.069508	-1.041869
C	-2.597	1.15101	1.14303	C	-2.585204	1.150532	1.138829
C	-2.4852	-0.69848	-0.59953	C	-2.473447	-0.698992	-0.603716
C	-3.45316	0.38041	0.25803	C	-3.441391	0.379934	0.253835
C	-2.12131	2.49049	-1.64083	C	-2.109567	2.490028	-1.645025
O	-0.06863	-0.55037	-0.34807	O	-0.056834	-0.550878	-0.352221
O	-3.15796	-1.16181	-1.72334	O	-3.14614	-1.162275	-1.727542
N	-4.56302	-0.2624	0.97179	N	-4.551196	-0.262861	0.967619
O	4.15526	1.84049	0.29334	O	4.167046	1.839921	0.289173
C	4.78675	-1.30333	-1.02877	C	4.798614	-1.3038	-1.032926
O	5.91641	-0.79657	-0.9447	O	5.928215	-0.797041	-0.948869
C	4.53424	-2.80022	-1.3631	C	4.546024	-2.800722	-1.367283
O	-3.37835	1.79374	-1.90461	O	-3.366523	1.793186	-1.90874
C	-5.32967	-1.36726	0.53801	C	-5.317857	-1.367767	0.533777
C	-6.51756	-1.67701	1.4758	C	-6.505779	-1.677484	1.471651
O	-5.07803	-2.05728	-0.4821	O	-5.066221	-2.057773	-0.48629
H	0.97441	1.92098	1.36716	H	0.986093	1.920689	1.363104
H	3.47431	0.4206	1.80345	H	3.486169	0.42023	1.799128
H	3.15155	3.00534	1.76396	H	3.1633	3.00485	1.759632
H	2.6884	3.37414	0.0624	H	2.700172	3.373771	0.058151
H	1.13167	-0.075	-2.04267	H	1.143485	-0.075435	-2.047152
H	2.18743	-0.25323	3.54998	H	2.199786	-0.254301	3.545848
H	1.12359	-1.45856	1.31089	H	1.135138	-1.459036	1.306669
H	2.89984	-2.8965	1.45839	H	2.911171	-2.897501	1.453712
H	2.16544	-2.03718	-0.90387	H	2.177277	-2.037783	-0.908102
H	-0.13386	1.93272	-0.78429	H	-0.121427	1.932131	-0.788422
H	3.83013	0.47518	-0.5094	H	3.841943	0.475173	-0.513166
H	-1.10927	-0.02186	-2.14185	H	-1.097472	-0.022273	-2.14625
H	-2.75267	1.22849	2.24088	H	-2.740938	1.228022	2.237061
H	-2.21396	-1.47067	0.15718	H	-2.202076	-1.471278	0.153231
H	-3.70745	1.06334	-0.66386	H	-3.695509	1.063266	-0.66837
H	-1.57488	2.66784	-2.58784	H	-1.562928	2.667455	-2.592184
H	-2.28434	3.47066	-1.14848	H	-2.272516	3.47039	-1.152571
H	-3.99604	-1.64222	-1.29906	H	-3.984471	-1.642635	-1.302529
H	-4.92645	0.22833	1.8098	H	-4.914754	0.228119	1.805995
H	4.81081	2.54921	-0.00157	H	4.822814	2.54951	-0.005886
H	5.49161	-3.26265	-1.62344	H	5.503462	-3.26318	-1.627647
H	3.84645	-2.8992	-2.21043	H	3.858233	-2.89971	-2.214628
H	4.11444	-3.33008	-0.50111	H	4.126215	-3.330564	-0.505288
H	-3.96685	2.47075	-2.37169	H	-3.955231	2.471014	-2.376035
H	-7.04149	-2.56209	1.10008	H	-7.029746	-2.562656	1.095875
H	-7.21037	-0.82635	1.49955	H	-7.198598	-0.826776	1.495382
H	-6.1542	-1.87168	2.49262	H	-6.142381	-1.872158	2.488497

368 (TS)

	x	y	z
C	1.39697	1.85793	-0.20088
C	2.7801	1.15258	-0.17198
C	0.53583	1.552	1.09439
O	1.60265	3.37181	-0.26777
O	3.44415	1.53677	-1.27666
C	2.42215	-0.42756	0.00868
C	-0.90931	2.33826	0.82474
O	0.22561	0.17093	1.14366

368 (GS)

	x	y	z
C	1.388048	1.90572	-0.244073
C	2.742585	1.133765	-0.129436
C	0.469786	1.657042	0.99422
O	1.685746	3.309822	-0.381412
O	3.444676	1.565552	-1.291118
C	2.422713	-0.398791	-0.005835
C	-0.908811	2.367124	0.81017
O	0.226176	0.199825	1.129082

C	1.5116	-0.58768	1.28222	C	1.512175	-0.558848	1.267686
N	3.61165	-1.26799	0.27142	N	3.612226	-1.239178	0.256881
O	1.19676	-1.96381	1.46001	O	1.197333	-1.934993	1.44547
O	-1.48558	2.07492	-0.49179	O	-1.485013	2.103739	-0.506336
C	-2.24148	0.87535	-0.55765	C	-2.2409	0.904164	-0.572191
O	-1.26961	-0.28001	-0.62689	O	-1.269039	-0.251196	-0.641437
C	-3.30566	0.577	0.58294	C	-3.305079	0.605818	0.568402
C	4.89827	-1.10982	-0.2999	C	4.898855	-1.081002	-0.314446
C	-1.91444	-1.62078	-0.67101	C	-1.913857	-1.591966	-0.685549
C	-4.1885	-0.65311	0.10076	C	-4.187921	-0.624293	0.08622
O	-4.14796	1.71452	0.78065	O	-4.147379	1.743337	0.766109
C	-3.44768	-1.522	-0.98863	C	-3.447098	-1.49319	-1.003169
C	-1.65478	-2.39101	0.64336	C	-1.654204	-2.362194	0.628817
O	-5.37832	-0.03526	-0.47463	O	-5.377744	-0.006445	-0.489173
O	-3.90037	-2.89783	-1.00452	O	-3.899792	-2.869016	-1.019059
C	5.81977	-2.32114	-0.02046	C	5.820347	-2.292323	-0.034996
O	5.28898	-0.09406	-0.92239	O	5.289568	-0.065255	-0.936923
H	0.84579	1.47917	-1.11597	H	0.846225	1.507702	-1.131039
H	3.24748	1.39268	0.83447	H	3.247994	1.421444	0.820383
H	0.9459	1.97864	1.94627	H	0.945577	2.007142	1.929944
H	2.51579	3.18991	-0.95478	H	2.518852	3.217684	-0.971126
H	4.31615	0.97171	-1.21751	H	4.316568	1.00056	-1.23196
H	1.86268	-0.7741	-0.88359	H	1.863268	-0.745242	-0.898145
H	-1.59834	2.09879	1.6537	H	-1.597706	2.127597	1.639186
H	-0.69766	3.42306	0.83971	H	-0.697199	3.451937	0.825179
H	2.02523	-0.12737	2.15769	H	2.025831	-0.098558	2.143142
H	3.37878	-2.22487	0.60329	H	3.379342	-2.196044	0.588739
H	0.97554	-2.04634	2.44634	H	0.976114	-2.017524	2.431797
H	-2.74508	0.90937	-1.54759	H	-2.7445	0.938191	-1.56213
H	-0.49706	-0.15794	0.23651	H	-0.496357	-0.129223	0.222126
H	-2.76612	0.31195	1.51185	H	-2.765541	0.340767	1.497309
H	-1.42161	-2.15061	-1.50993	H	-1.421028	-2.121792	-1.524471
H	-4.43207	-1.29927	0.96312	H	-4.431487	-1.270457	0.94858
H	-4.94233	1.40631	0.19526	H	-4.941747	1.435125	0.180726
H	-3.58433	-1.02704	-1.97162	H	-3.583754	-0.998227	-1.986158
H	-2.07716	-3.39515	0.52564	H	-2.076582	-3.366336	0.511104
H	-2.14473	-1.9013	1.491	H	-2.144152	-1.872487	1.476463
H	-0.5746	-2.4597	0.83447	H	-0.574024	-2.430881	0.819931
H	-6.14613	-0.40852	0.06802	H	-6.145548	-0.379711	0.053484
H	-4.80889	-2.82456	-1.45317	H	-4.808307	-2.795746	-1.467712
H	6.81539	-2.10955	-0.42407	H	6.815971	-2.08073	-0.43861
H	5.4165	-3.22064	-0.50207	H	5.417081	-3.191828	-0.516606
H	5.89285	-2.49703	1.05969	H	5.893427	-2.468218	1.045152

Table S7.

Frequency analysis of mass spectrometric species of carbohydrates in ground (GS) and transition (TS) states in gas-phase at M062X level of theory; symbols of carbohydrate (syb-)units

488 (GS)							
■-2-AB							
▲							
Frequencies	15.4688	19.406	27.6451	Frequencies	1116.1408	1128.0615	1129.5852
Frequencies	32.5372	42.7314	46.4136	Frequencies	1142.3065	1146.8396	1149.5235
Frequencies	54.0817	72.1257	80.7627	Frequencies	1157.971	1171.4017	1180.448
Frequencies	85.5239	90.4067	104.9923	Frequencies	1188.4602	1206.3785	1211.4733
Frequencies	107.6703	117.7938	119.8072	Frequencies	1214.5272	1215.0795	1220.1818
Frequencies	131.4995	138.5865	151.4003	Frequencies	1228.3427	1238.2134	1241.3933
Frequencies	175.7261	181.6359	194.2295	Frequencies	1246.5367	1250.3197	1255.0627
Frequencies	198.4365	217.0993	228.6189	Frequencies	1270.6507	1277.7443	1293.8375
Frequencies	254.2033	263.9448	267.8186	Frequencies	1295.6306	1305.7182	1322.2883
Frequencies	275.6619	291.9874	300.4371	Frequencies	1328.0804	1339.4535	1347.583
Frequencies	307.3027	323.3588	340.0095	Frequencies	1359.4997	1362.4399	1371.0952
Frequencies	346.5848	362.876	378.6762	Frequencies	1376.8386	1386.4122	1395.7235
Frequencies	388.3695	398.8217	417.0406	Frequencies	1402.4692	1405.8618	1409.0527
Frequencies	423.4288	428.7744	444.187	Frequencies	1418.1289	1429.7823	1434.6178
Frequencies	464.6108	468.8868	488.1758	Frequencies	1679.4814	1699.1952	1702.2425
Frequencies	497.0871	508.5934	531.0039	Frequencies	1756.083	1768.7338	1776.3588
Frequencies	541.6195	552.9014	577.7833	Frequencies	1796.5924	1817.9225	1889.3974
Frequencies	582.3419	589.7893	593.2366	Frequencies	1915.9045	2020.9186	2572.5471
Frequencies	610.8361	616.2199	631.9419	Frequencies	2989.4507	3325.46	3339.8336
Frequencies	646.2489	658.623	661.4032	Frequencies	3350.7826	3351.4125	3359.9035
Frequencies	687.7715	710.8359	713.6083	Frequencies	3365.9367	3374.9358	3384.0601
Frequencies	721.9126	763.8985	774.7738	Frequencies	3384.5812	3392.3237	3393.6805
Frequencies	779.7195	794.5566	825.5548	Frequencies	3394.9561	3399.0561	3420.3503
Frequencies	836.1027	875.9429	884.9403	Frequencies	3494.5455	3509.4787	3513.8302
Frequencies	916.5896	926.146	945.8679	Frequencies	3521.0148	3530.7167	3530.7929
Frequencies	966.0088	970.0197	988.9974	Frequencies	3542.102	3545.2233	3561.7362
Frequencies	997.4715	1049.6055	1055.1015	Frequencies	3568.7366	3573.0018	3634.0396
Frequencies	1060.7981	1073.8311	1077.7518	Frequencies	3669.9102	3688.3715	3817.238
Frequencies	1087.5219	1096.287	1098.3541	Frequencies	3823.4883	3875.5789	3887.4882
488 (TS)							
■-2-AB							
▲							
Frequencies	-74.3529	13.3628	22.5729	Frequencies	1212.879	1214.3936	1215.8496
Frequencies	27.6852	42.3635	44.6518	Frequencies	1229.4987	1238.2702	1240.8427
Frequencies	48.2922	69.7362	77.8872	Frequencies	1246.9608	1249.6469	1254.9338
Frequencies	85.57	87.011	102.5544	Frequencies	1259.9938	1283.9728	1296.5724
Frequencies	109.6545	117.4589	119.3548	Frequencies	1303.8893	1305.0715	1327.9479
Frequencies	130.5782	137.1789	151.3669	Frequencies	1332.0493	1346.3786	1357.1252
Frequencies	175.321	181.7455	193.2798	Frequencies	1359.9715	1366.9231	1370.7491
Frequencies	201.9071	217.2992	229.4625	Frequencies	1374.1169	1379.7462	1395.4016
Frequencies	248.8756	263.3575	267.3409	Frequencies	1405.25	1407.5147	1407.8807
Frequencies	282.1033	288.5345	301.9753	Frequencies	1419.5143	1429.4312	1433.115
Frequencies	307.2886	321.5663	340.4667	Frequencies	1434.6913	1451.503	1454.9672
Frequencies	346.4443	360.8152	378.2258	Frequencies	1480.7875	1487.1965	1496.1114
Frequencies	388.9255	397.1409	416.3371	Frequencies	1499.4663	1512.6058	1520.068
Frequencies	422.3912	429.0148	443.8915	Frequencies	1546.0704	1552.4063	1560.2276
Frequencies	465.6218	471.0443	489.6569	Frequencies	1574.101	1575.631	1580.111
Frequencies	496.7913	506.9801	524.0627	Frequencies	1592.6926	1594.9803	1631.8997
Frequencies	543.0327	557.0941	577.1717	Frequencies	1634.1012	1649.7707	1657.1006
Frequencies	582.9204	590.3805	594.1489	Frequencies	1661.3491	1667.4197	1667.9911
Frequencies	609.6521	615.2669	630.8597	Frequencies	1679.5049	1684.3082	1698.9095

Frequencies	1520.4331	1524.1953	1540.9118	Frequencies	1658.9178	1663.5442	1677.0033
Frequencies	1547.712	1594.1011	1599.9978	Frequencies	1684.3048	1735.9536	1751.3083
Frequencies	1647.962	1718.6879	1766.1121	Frequencies	1781.6444	1898.1698	1947.2199
Frequencies	2042.6343	2474.0757	2815.0384	Frequencies	2474.6295	3206.8649	3244.0734
Frequencies	2961.3831	2994.3149	3000.3786	Frequencies	3336.1425	3348.7078	3358.1821
Frequencies	3003.1864	3014.6863	3022.8429	Frequencies	3362.5204	3374.8912	3376.091
Frequencies	3027.5219	3052.7176	3054.0543	Frequencies	3379.2447	3381.2808	3382.2861
Frequencies	3054.8757	3063.2398	3100.6619	Frequencies	3383.8319	3404.7079	3436.319
Frequencies	3134.7545	3150.8127	3159.2951	Frequencies	3460.6395	3460.9592	3466.5983
Frequencies	3173.3261	3178.3591	3287.7189	Frequencies	3544.5214	3550.6036	3563.7322
Frequencies	3301.8936	3309.5496	3356.1019	Frequencies	3568.6497	3821.7796	3843.6535
Frequencies	3378.5025	3379.5219	3695.8323	Frequencies	3846.9944	3893.394	3909.7528

366_yb_a (GS)

Frequencies	30.2727	37.2879	53.8314	Frequencies	1192.2192	1211.2886	1215.55
Frequencies	62.6669	70.8834	81.6284	Frequencies	1224.4515	1226.2521	1235.9127
Frequencies	87.8206	103.9521	124.7427	Frequencies	1264.5119	1280.6393	1288.4018
Frequencies	138.279	153.8665	162.5959	Frequencies	1298.0003	1299.9627	1319.7818
Frequencies	176.2959	194.1349	199.1668	Frequencies	1326.336	1332.2568	1354.2727
Frequencies	217.5674	246.0787	258.2845	Frequencies	1359.569	1364.3939	1373.6724
Frequencies	277.2276	310.8527	326.6174	Frequencies	1379.9476	1386.7207	1403.3042
Frequencies	333.7511	338.6746	360.7169	Frequencies	1406.0097	1419.5976	1424.397
Frequencies	367.6705	385.6144	393.3989	Frequencies	1437.5083	1440.4159	1451.528
Frequencies	424.4591	440.8138	445.0307	Frequencies	1465.714	1476.7635	1483.9427
Frequencies	466.0431	483.0648	499.8324	Frequencies	1508.6806	1512.1324	1534.5848
Frequencies	509.265	510.6838	519.836	Frequencies	1546.5872	1558.9208	1606.5356
Frequencies	529.5166	542.4731	549.2723	Frequencies	1622.8748	1634.905	1642.0816
Frequencies	562.7439	629.7469	639.6334	Frequencies	1651.3528	1668.4523	1668.844
Frequencies	645.117	688.0764	722.7442	Frequencies	1696.8614	1725.1852	1766.9043
Frequencies	733.1891	760.2539	769.0106	Frequencies	1821.5591	1917.9717	1958.8559
Frequencies	852.6871	856.1869	877.0541	Frequencies	1996.1276	2997.7217	3307.4511
Frequencies	885.0289	898.3662	982.0653	Frequencies	3336.7135	3339.3557	3347.4109
Frequencies	997.4359	1012.1042	1027.5745	Frequencies	3372.7839	3381.0711	3383.2327
Frequencies	1057.2547	1061.149	1062.0434	Frequencies	3385.3066	3391.9888	3399.7957
Frequencies	1067.3707	1100.9252	1117.0158	Frequencies	3406.6292	3423.7971	3434.8893
Frequencies	1122.4691	1143.1782	1150.7098	Frequencies	3442.5057	3502.8388	3545.2105
Frequencies	1154.9419	1165.1397	1184.9475				

366_yb_a (TS)

Frequencies	-14.6485	27.3762	48.368	Frequencies	1225.0918	1233.3409	1260.2923
Frequencies	65.542	71.6155	79.918	Frequencies	1265.0857	1280.334	1293.4877
Frequencies	85.8445	100.156	120.3785	Frequencies	1295.0937	1300.6309	1309.7607
Frequencies	134.5451	152.2413	153.5777	Frequencies	1324.6668	1332.2214	1360.6239
Frequencies	174.9237	193.9878	200.2446	Frequencies	1364.6285	1366.5338	1370.9102
Frequencies	210.1896	240.9517	252.1837	Frequencies	1379.611	1381.5324	1394.4419
Frequencies	273.2704	310.4759	323.5654	Frequencies	1410.5161	1419.5551	1430.8281
Frequencies	334.0268	340.6718	360.191	Frequencies	1439.2207	1450.526	1453.2423
Frequencies	367.4912	387.2548	392.8226	Frequencies	1466.582	1483.6534	1496.9308
Frequencies	425.6778	442.3816	447.7466	Frequencies	1510.4721	1521.3075	1534.3762
Frequencies	467.1621	480.9543	499.1069	Frequencies	1558.1248	1606.3795	1618.2658
Frequencies	508.0614	509.2237	512.8175	Frequencies	1622.0616	1625.9112	1642.2784
Frequencies	527.5364	542.5431	553.0056	Frequencies	1651.2473	1667.8168	1670.1459

Frequencies	563.4403	617.6013	636.164	Frequencies 1677.6944 1703.2958 1765.5509
Frequencies	646.3506	684.0189	730.2179	Frequencies 1818.7802 1916.771 1964.3148
Frequencies	735.9501	763.657	784.4623	Frequencies 1994.691 2997.3025 3291.9336
Frequencies	830.0408	856.0911	871.2904	Frequencies 3307.3129 3320.61 3336.8223
Frequencies	897.257	904.3335	968.8617	Frequencies 3339.6216 3347.5566 3381.6842
Frequencies	983.9578	1011.532	1024.0633	Frequencies 3385.5122 3387.3941 3399.7465
Frequencies	1056.8649	1059.3269	1061.396	Frequencies 3406.6389 3434.7066 3442.7105
Frequencies	1067.4434	1107.6908	1119.21	Frequencies 3466.0613 3503.0672 3545.7098
Frequencies	1124.1809	1142.1966	1152.819	Frequencies 3564.4335 3710.6586 3758.3942
Frequencies	1154.6558	1161.0799	1185.5581	Frequencies 3804.4737 3872.4354 3876.8743
Frequencies	1191.9267	1212.4511	1216.3405	

366_yb_b (GS)

Frequencies	31.9679	44.0636	55.3977	Frequencies 1234.1344 1237.8312 1258.3667
Frequencies	57.7553	76.6721	79.748	Frequencies 1263.1204 1279.2994 1285.9203
Frequencies	99.9996	105.547	121.08	Frequencies 1296.4988 1309.3678 1318.2853
Frequencies	141.1038	144.8735	168.7003	Frequencies 1333.2527 1340.0168 1352.5733
Frequencies	206.8073	225.5405	241.0101	Frequencies 1365.5457 1375.7944 1377.9803
Frequencies	248.3421	254.2009	258.387	Frequencies 1380.7104 1385.223 1401.4481
Frequencies	286.6814	296.1873	310.2801	Frequencies 1411.5042 1422.991 1441.8754
Frequencies	322.4701	332.2713	343.4508	Frequencies 1451.5325 1456.3778 1471.8585
Frequencies	366.5412	383.5299	391.1633	Frequencies 1481.7384 1487.4723 1504.8543
Frequencies	417.9352	428.8843	442.226	Frequencies 1513.1893 1526.8506 1550.7682
Frequencies	453.7366	478.8232	496.5803	Frequencies 1568.4445 1573.8957 1604.8459
Frequencies	502.2093	516.9557	527.0929	Frequencies 1608.2014 1625.3156 1633.5851
Frequencies	544.6312	560.1346	563.6501	Frequencies 1638.5161 1659.9475 1669.6259
Frequencies	585.9361	619.4898	660.4249	Frequencies 1678.4201 1776.6838 1821.3188
Frequencies	685.3892	715.0545	728.9256	Frequencies 1905.8137 1948.0283 2186.5825
Frequencies	789.1473	825.6115	860.1806	Frequencies 2301.9861 2928.0428 3067.6422
Frequencies	874.9078	886.1561	903.7732	Frequencies 3279.4742 3334.1508 3366.4779
Frequencies	913.956	933.0015	946.745	Frequencies 3370.605 3382.9617 3385.1476
Frequencies	985.6973	1007.0131	1037.6762	Frequencies 3391.7912 3406.0714 3411.1046
Frequencies	1046.9008	1086.1947	1089.6272	Frequencies 3435.7757 3445.1294 3474.5431
Frequencies	1111.2365	1121.6737	1129.8553	Frequencies 3503.5715 3543.3928 3549.3528
Frequencies	1147.731	1162.1239	1167.5971	Frequencies 3564.7547 3759.4578 3840.3326
Frequencies	1182.2049	1195.5007	1205.5378	Frequencies 3856.9824 3872.0585 3928.227
Frequencies	1207.0678	1221.1525	1228.5587	

366_yb_b (TS)

Frequencies	-47.7498	27.3203	46.6188	Frequencies 1235.0454 1239.633 1250.1258
Frequencies	50.1246	74.3317	81.7566	Frequencies 1261.5121 1273.5778 1285.6342
Frequencies	100.9617	108.6049	121.3836	Frequencies 1290.613 1309.2219 1320.2456
Frequencies	130.9218	144.5464	169.6294	Frequencies 1336.7646 1347.5346 1352.7111
Frequencies	208.216	223.6076	241.1549	Frequencies 1365.9233 1375.3591 1381.0595
Frequencies	247.783	251.9962	259.7349	Frequencies 1381.9751 1386.2339 1401.8183
Frequencies	286.7157	300.1344	313.4584	Frequencies 1411.6716 1423.2142 1440.6392
Frequencies	323.5136	325.4632	332.3232	Frequencies 1452.7929 1453.9417 1472.0192
Frequencies	366.4898	384.1421	392.6075	Frequencies 1481.7699 1486.4898 1497.8296
Frequencies	399.2036	418.9727	429.6696	Frequencies 1512.1581 1525.7653 1545.9665
Frequencies	448.293	469.327	481.7606	Frequencies 1551.0592 1573.7528 1597.319
Frequencies	500.2037	502.2199	523.2126	Frequencies 1605.381 1624.9118 1633.591

Frequencies	534.0274	549.3584	562.8989	Frequencies	1638.0329	1663.6744	1669.5869
Frequencies	585.8462	587.1328	621.0244	Frequencies	1676.9809	1776.6013	1820.97
Frequencies	662.5725	708.667	728.2676	Frequencies	1837.489	1947.6516	2186.5097
Frequencies	788.6193	809.7345	860.1528	Frequencies	2301.8106	2928.3855	3067.9057
Frequencies	881.1821	886.3278	903.7467	Frequencies	3276.9143	3334.1609	3367.5489
Frequencies	916.4989	945.5517	960.5891	Frequencies	3370.6731	3383.4428	3385.634
Frequencies	993.9337	1007.0569	1037.6456	Frequencies	3393.5619	3411.1661	3429.3226
Frequencies	1045.6098	1086.1318	1089.3559	Frequencies	3435.7774	3444.6558	3445.2271
Frequencies	1102.5608	1120.9125	1129.7466	Frequencies	3474.6038	3503.6677	3549.5722
Frequencies	1153.17	1162.1248	1163.8074	Frequencies	3565.4051	3844.2783	3857.1984
Frequencies	1180.2191	1183.6411	1200.6868	Frequencies	3872.0015	3914.9233	3928.281
Frequencies	1206.7879	1221.136	1228.6318				

292_a (GS)

Frequencies	31.5212	42.327	45.279	Frequencies	1193.1839	1208.7701	1219.3619
Frequencies	69.1562	71.1915	108.3531	Frequencies	1225.2562	1238.3371	1259.4126
Frequencies	135.9889	145.2156	148.9624	Frequencies	1275.862	1283.722	1290.2942
Frequencies	165.9805	179.6946	199.0367	Frequencies	1309.8569	1318.4298	1337.9818
Frequencies	216.1625	246.6878	268.259	Frequencies	1361.5848	1371.0534	1392.6109
Frequencies	310.7098	322.437	339.605	Frequencies	1405.076	1424.9996	1453.5412
Frequencies	361.5127	381.6623	395.8094	Frequencies	1467.7753	1471.9107	1481.9335
Frequencies	415.5817	427.3968	443.2797	Frequencies	1518.9516	1523.7988	1540.8138
Frequencies	482.2843	510.6343	533.8162	Frequencies	1551.848	1584.8754	1608.2302
Frequencies	555.2201	564.714	608.4656	Frequencies	1616.87	1629.2933	1637.1173
Frequencies	613.8856	634.5384	653.8983	Frequencies	1661.322	1666.4948	1670.6728
Frequencies	667.4411	691.8433	708.6392	Frequencies	1898.4453	1954.006	1977.6123
Frequencies	756.2051	774.4641	830.1366	Frequencies	2423.9536	3358.7653	3367.5672
Frequencies	869.6675	918.719	961.0247	Frequencies	3380.1158	3383.5021	3410.0564
Frequencies	971.8548	978.2262	1009.2757	Frequencies	3418.8315	3421.9347	3453.7613
Frequencies	1055.1189	1069.1323	1094.5633	Frequencies	3500.5137	3531.7202	3546.3521
Frequencies	1107.2588	1122.2187	1125.84	Frequencies	3571.4429	3732.7396	3852.3622
Frequencies	1141.6772	1174.7045	1188.3846	Frequencies	3852.9482	3861.2403	3932.0844

292_a (TS)

Frequencies	-34.749	41.298	43.8268	Frequencies	1204.8574	1216.8612	1220.8399
Frequencies	66.5141	69.9733	110.8457	Frequencies	1236.2478	1252.363	1266.7888
Frequencies	129.416	145.0526	151.4499	Frequencies	1277.968	1282.333	1313.0396
Frequencies	161.4498	177.5205	201.3686	Frequencies	1326.174	1339.9452	1351.3201
Frequencies	217.4236	246.9246	268.774	Frequencies	1379.9367	1382.5102	1408.3085
Frequencies	311.2307	323.3006	340.6114	Frequencies	1427.0763	1447.3037	1466.6375
Frequencies	360.2794	387.9659	395.6492	Frequencies	1494.2745	1514.9217	1519.0326
Frequencies	414.172	428.6119	446.6722	Frequencies	1531.6602	1538.9347	1540.7004
Frequencies	487.1613	505.6707	534.1266	Frequencies	1552.0148	1595.6486	1621.3546
Frequencies	557.9519	564.9349	610.896	Frequencies	1632.0698	1633.7906	1663.1449
Frequencies	619.0311	635.0367	648.7524	Frequencies	1666.3438	1670.6574	1678.0555
Frequencies	667.232	687.3563	704.8457	Frequencies	1905.2728	1953.948	1981.5485
Frequencies	749.4407	778.2627	823.4036	Frequencies	2422.6447	2988.6055	3243.1641
Frequencies	853.8081	910.1649	960.3783	Frequencies	3360.0929	3361.9139	3381.1244
Frequencies	973.3715	975.4636	1008.7928	Frequencies	3383.8122	3418.6548	3501.6174
Frequencies	1044.3896	1068.1891	1070.655	Frequencies	3517.2623	3531.7857	3546.5025

Frequencies	1096.526	1124.0105	1126.328	Frequencies	3571.7282	3730.1591	3852.277
Frequencies	1146.3509	1176.3105	1197.9348	Frequencies	3855.043	3860.6354	3932.1295

292_b (TS)

Frequencies	-39.8057	33.327	46.3444	Frequencies	1208.1774	1226.1756	1229.0917
Frequencies	56.4689	69.5001	97.1578	Frequencies	1250.197	1271.9607	1279.8781
Frequencies	111.794	130.7299	146.8626	Frequencies	1283.3805	1300.2427	1305.2033
Frequencies	156.609	170.807	177.5599	Frequencies	1320.0148	1340.0935	1372.8806
Frequencies	207.1198	234.5777	268.476	Frequencies	1384.9052	1399.3355	1436.9461
Frequencies	277.4798	297.9403	325.1312	Frequencies	1443.3192	1450.8623	1487.5816
Frequencies	362.9356	368.3079	398.5663	Frequencies	1501.1603	1512.4717	1519.7857
Frequencies	410.9139	420.5248	429.1549	Frequencies	1532.4106	1551.9968	1575.2423
Frequencies	478.4541	488.0266	514.2516	Frequencies	1584.2496	1606.2785	1629.2005
Frequencies	544.9023	573.9743	587.3593	Frequencies	1631.8142	1647.6165	1653.763
Frequencies	602.9218	634.2996	655.059	Frequencies	1664.4493	1667.17	1723.1117
Frequencies	665.3994	681.4856	692.3896	Frequencies	1941.9454	1970.2534	1984.2558
Frequencies	710.568	745.0617	814.0106	Frequencies	2426.5264	2593.0961	2982.7429
Frequencies	868.8303	904.7445	959.3292	Frequencies	3371.8853	3375.1949	3382.5742
Frequencies	966.3745	981.7103	1033.8502	Frequencies	3384.5441	3415.1171	3472.4831
Frequencies	1070.4971	1084.1462	1093.6424	Frequencies	3501.8811	3527.1964	3545.0034
Frequencies	1117.4916	1124.1429	1141.5358	Frequencies	3569.5408	3745.7128	3847.7051
Frequencies	1147.1852	1163.432	1195.3621	Frequencies	3864.6865	3874.709	3937.9594

292_b (GS)

Frequencies	39.4645	40.0105	59.3689	Frequencies	1187.3841	1200.9194	1213.3752
Frequencies	64.1097	80.1127	105.7475	Frequencies	1227.7783	1233.2142	1268.1553
Frequencies	112.836	141.9651	151.5262	Frequencies	1278.9116	1283.0302	1293.9421
Frequencies	163.3285	171.3542	178.5045	Frequencies	1303.58	1322.6225	1328.9562
Frequencies	202.0339	234.4751	263.5509	Frequencies	1334.7441	1359.1432	1390.3208
Frequencies	276.2836	298.8722	326.4719	Frequencies	1417.8633	1438.5727	1440.8998
Frequencies	362.4089	371.7992	401.3014	Frequencies	1458.4457	1470.1151	1493.9523
Frequencies	407.9445	415.4638	430.4616	Frequencies	1501.937	1515.8327	1518.3523
Frequencies	471.0102	486.2442	516.264	Frequencies	1551.2065	1571.4607	1604.9089
Frequencies	541.8942	569.5093	574.5209	Frequencies	1625.5926	1629.5757	1643.9966
Frequencies	602.6093	634.3838	654.7132	Frequencies	1654.4258	1664.5293	1667.1494
Frequencies	672.3193	675.2301	697.9836	Frequencies	1942.2818	1944.7846	1983.4516
Frequencies	706.6336	739.0607	833.7289	Frequencies	2431.2564	3375.1717	3382.1083
Frequencies	896.4925	914.1133	960.4775	Frequencies	3382.3196	3386.3048	3387.2242
Frequencies	975.3093	990.6261	1040.2704	Frequencies	3393.5738	3414.2237	3447.2967
Frequencies	1066.0936	1090.778	1093.2005	Frequencies	3500.8248	3526.5521	3544.9008
Frequencies	1122.3658	1123.551	1129.4276	Frequencies	3569.2932	3749.7461	3848.0064
Frequencies	1141.558	1160.9818	1184.1825	Frequencies	3862.3006	3875.0523	3938.099

291_a (TS)

Frequencies	-60.0584	16.8948	31.369	Frequencies	1205.007	1215.1824	1225.7018
Frequencies	44.3243	57.0178	69.9201	Frequencies	1256.3407	1262.2885	1286.109
Frequencies	89.1689	105.7405	117.3965	Frequencies	1298.5059	1311.977	1325.8567
Frequencies	134.4843	166.4923	186.3564	Frequencies	1349.7959	1355.926	1377.5497
Frequencies	213.2081	243.2388	252.6761	Frequencies	1399.8072	1406.3486	1441.2713
Frequencies	268.5641	317.4539	340.2693	Frequencies	1444.9181	1472.2338	1473.9973

Frequencies	367.2403	393.2068	398.4413	Frequencies	1522.6799	1539.5131	1540.7667
Frequencies	428.0616	442.7838	454.5162	Frequencies	1552.8624	1584.6739	1628.8932
Frequencies	488.2775	506.6577	520.7987	Frequencies	1648.3054	1666.5825	1672.1286
Frequencies	530.8958	554.5972	579.0019	Frequencies	1673.752	1688.6066	1886.1999
Frequencies	601.1269	610.2642	619.7532	Frequencies	1919.5479	1950.0147	1955.8049
Frequencies	651.8219	676.9771	680.8473	Frequencies	2047.1542	2496.5165	2866.2835
Frequencies	711.8086	734.6163	777.1278	Frequencies	3264.6738	3335.1088	3378.7527
Frequencies	789.0619	882.8299	937.8803	Frequencies	3382.268	3391.5861	3421.4356
Frequencies	968.5099	982.1148	1029.3171	Frequencies	3495.9731	3545.5354	3553.0372
Frequencies	1058.6125	1068.5036	1084.1448	Frequencies	3569.3522	3797.7047	3849.1499
Frequencies	1102.1639	1114.6465	1120.4203	Frequencies	3857.3549	3879.732	3918.3965
Frequencies	1167.0143	1190.3297	1203.3014				

291_a (GS)

Frequencies	26.2246	32.9834	40.1915	Frequencies	1189.9086	1199.3116	1205.0194
Frequencies	51.6366	68.5079	73.1309	Frequencies	1227.589	1229.1266	1251.2753
Frequencies	103.102	111.4248	116.5721	Frequencies	1310.1696	1318.3758	1323.1744
Frequencies	140.2083	164.6427	185.3622	Frequencies	1354.4287	1375.1275	1379.0843
Frequencies	218.4045	243.4774	253.788	Frequencies	1399.1654	1429.4342	1436.1104
Frequencies	275.2329	325.0834	332.3343	Frequencies	1452.6936	1461.5691	1476.1676
Frequencies	376.3818	390.3139	407.9061	Frequencies	1487.5371	1534.5658	1542.4309
Frequencies	430.9555	442.7371	453.0177	Frequencies	1553.0207	1587.5792	1593.6422
Frequencies	484.3915	504.4804	526.0793	Frequencies	1645.424	1666.6897	1667.628
Frequencies	531.5339	558.067	585.9482	Frequencies	1673.4665	1693.3729	1868.4558
Frequencies	610.8759	616.3812	628.7125	Frequencies	1916.4524	1947.0538	1954.687
Frequencies	660.8843	673.5499	693.1664	Frequencies	2044.6131	2535.7324	2874.4505
Frequencies	722.2553	741.0495	793.3095	Frequencies	3335.2195	3379.1778	3382.4491
Frequencies	802.2845	882.3227	953.7986	Frequencies	3392.3505	3395.4389	3418.4931
Frequencies	962.1403	1007.8913	1059.6488	Frequencies	3427.5296	3496.0482	3544.541
Frequencies	1070.8472	1085.0232	1105.2896	Frequencies	3545.7508	3569.4317	3850.8345
Frequencies	1120.6406	1124.6217	1143.5619	Frequencies	3856.9115	3876.9022	3917.8222
Frequencies	1263.6055	1280.7856	1295.9663				

271_b (TS)

Frequencies	-258.7727	31.8218	54.393	Frequencies	1193.5908	1205.588	1220.8895
Frequencies	60.4307	100.4468	121.4981	Frequencies	1227.5813	1243.7106	1266.4869
Frequencies	141.7849	142.9545	169.0748	Frequencies	1296.292	1304.8105	1341.3141
Frequencies	194.2675	212.4559	236.5795	Frequencies	1351.9692	1361.1445	1376.8378
Frequencies	263.2383	306.361	312.1853	Frequencies	1389.4553	1421.6471	1435.7828
Frequencies	328.775	339.5782	355.7685	Frequencies	1462.4274	1476.9625	1481.0559
Frequencies	385.2005	412.881	436.5027	Frequencies	1499.517	1526.2273	1530.4258
Frequencies	445.604	465.775	496.3795	Frequencies	1535.7692	1573.4378	1607.2097
Frequencies	521.9627	529.436	548.8599	Frequencies	1632.5357	1640.5529	1644.4382
Frequencies	564.6942	590.1242	644.8614	Frequencies	1686.4689	1830.7305	1946.8589
Frequencies	677.5467	694.6511	723.1233	Frequencies	1996.6058	2075.8599	2603.0445
Frequencies	782.0379	805.5445	861.5447	Frequencies	3258.3954	3314.4696	3340.4575
Frequencies	873.1204	907.0927	935.1144	Frequencies	3345.4344	3359.7527	3367.601
Frequencies	968.8234	987.7675	997.5802	Frequencies	3368.6799	3489.4948	3549.5063
Frequencies	1040.6226	1047.3577	1054.152	Frequencies	3597.1887	3597.8832	3785.2187
Frequencies	1101.8766	1108.1118	1134.2425	Frequencies	3823.3118	3871.3107	4043.4603

Frequencies	1169.484	1176.4018	1186.8326	
271_b (GS)				
◆				
GS				
Frequencies	50.1205	58.2373	71.356	Frequencies 1197.1055 1207.9382 1215.5759
Frequencies	90.4592	104.4435	115.8138	Frequencies 1226.7615 1246.8411 1270.6904
Frequencies	139.9042	144.6332	167.1741	Frequencies 1302.5907 1308.3413 1335.0647
Frequencies	192.9391	210.2951	236.3901	Frequencies 1345.1009 1359.799 1368.0448
Frequencies	251.9454	283.9775	313.8256	Frequencies 1376.3669 1415.5029 1426.5048
Frequencies	320.6788	330.5438	358.0984	Frequencies 1453.7049 1463.6459 1475.1231
Frequencies	361.7668	393.4625	435.2941	Frequencies 1492.6263 1509.7012 1545.1499
Frequencies	449.1895	491.1215	496.5306	Frequencies 1552.1261 1577.1259 1597.5892
Frequencies	534.3779	538.9524	566.7572	Frequencies 1635.9922 1642.1772 1668.048
Frequencies	576.3697	615.4747	654.8148	Frequencies 1671.8973 1807.8923 1947.0334
Frequencies	677.2945	693.7706	729.9695	Frequencies 2017.3673 2088.4191 2522.2448
Frequencies	778.7577	800.824	865.8649	Frequencies 3376.4626 3377.7268 3382.4814
Frequencies	873.7023	932.5334	940.9172	Frequencies 3394.9895 3397.6653 3401.7667
Frequencies	969.091	985.6486	999.209	Frequencies 3446.1603 3494.5392 3515.3417
Frequencies	1051.747	1059.2693	1068.2811	Frequencies 3547.199 3568.4926 3631.8529
Frequencies	1108.4664	1122.3418	1136.989	Frequencies 3853.1477 3893.4889 3934.3238
Frequencies	1171.3496	1179.6271	1189.889	
271_a (GS)				
◆				
Frequencies	38.2459	62.5333	70.7377	Frequencies 1199.5466 1214.847 1228.3828
Frequencies	89.0993	105.358	107.2939	Frequencies 1253.6897 1271.7834 1274.5916
Frequencies	142.1097	149.0929	158.5013	Frequencies 1297.726 1335.3786 1343.1163
Frequencies	204.7917	248.6843	254.6017	Frequencies 1349.359 1351.9189 1370.3918
Frequencies	264.7734	300.0251	311.8811	Frequencies 1382.3114 1390.5057 1402.4362
Frequencies	333.6003	349.5903	373.024	Frequencies 1423.6591 1451.0762 1458.8313
Frequencies	391.3262	400.7251	410.0393	Frequencies 1476.3832 1500.4806 1503.3818
Frequencies	429.1944	447.9508	476.0071	Frequencies 1555.8108 1581.0587 1609.4901
Frequencies	503.1096	527.1392	538.2491	Frequencies 1621.1632 1664.4127 1666.1986
Frequencies	560.7453	579.7237	590.4956	Frequencies 1671.3013 1687.9735 1756.5461
Frequencies	635.522	667.5307	683.6579	Frequencies 1956.7784 2169.9066 3349.4385
Frequencies	760.0466	828.2346	842.1342	Frequencies 3353.4326 3371.5111 3381.6663
Frequencies	877.4867	893.2035	953.3609	Frequencies 3384.7937 3408.3703 3416.4471
Frequencies	983.3248	1007.1695	1040.5732	Frequencies 3419.5268 3450.1618 3464.8611
Frequencies	1074.2493	1081.2883	1101.0829	Frequencies 3528.2738 3535.4553 3548.2908
Frequencies	1109.7267	1125.4943	1128.2726	Frequencies 3570.0371 3849.2967 3914.7114
Frequencies	1168.9071	1186.5924	1193.4176	
472_α_{2,6}				
◆●				
GS				
Frequencies --	8.2424	16.8948	31.0115	Frequencies -- 1221.2592 1224.6662 1225.4028
Frequencies --	37.3337	51.4994	59.5779	Frequencies -- 1228.0948 1238.6795 1247.6943
Frequencies --	65.5472	69.9224	76.5741	Frequencies -- 1252.7725 1253.3086 1258.2687
Frequencies --	85.8346	99.7209	119.8813	Frequencies -- 1271.1924 1281.1124 1283.4263
Frequencies --	130.5188	133.1176	135.4988	Frequencies -- 1296.8270 1306.9236 1320.1835
Frequencies --	159.8593	175.9133	182.8327	Frequencies -- 1327.4708 1334.5125 1357.0392
Frequencies --	192.9283	202.5467	207.4952	Frequencies -- 1363.3799 1374.3062 1374.5461
Frequencies --	224.3305	237.7461	252.2099	Frequencies -- 1388.2212 1389.2389 1395.4065

Frequencies -- 260.7861 271.9005 279.5728
Frequencies -- 301.8107 320.0270 321.3863
Frequencies -- 329.7712 332.6514 355.5062
Frequencies -- 356.4936 363.9478 373.0413
Frequencies -- 390.2365 393.6030 413.8863
Frequencies -- 420.4732 422.0007 427.5428
Frequencies -- 434.3086 448.6942 457.4338
Frequencies -- 462.5595 470.8058 477.3931
Frequencies -- 486.5020 500.3241 512.1412
Frequencies -- 539.1262 553.6209 562.3122
Frequencies -- 568.6648 580.6048 586.1445
Frequencies -- 612.2395 681.9826 689.5710
Frequencies -- 701.6084 712.4257 743.6957
Frequencies -- 778.5379 806.9910 815.6294
Frequencies -- 859.5247 886.3026 915.4594
Frequencies -- 916.6609 923.1838 969.4209
Frequencies -- 982.0640 1010.5752 1016.3607
Frequencies -- 1035.1866 1067.0507 1076.5060
Frequencies -- 1087.6392 1112.0475 1115.1150
Frequencies -- 1122.2418 1124.1267 1136.6205
Frequencies -- 1149.7055 1156.1695 1167.6481
Frequencies -- 1184.1647 1202.6514 1204.2381

472_α_{2,6}

GS

Frequencies -- -24.0170 13.1520 21.9464
Frequencies -- 34.9638 44.9241 56.7227
Frequencies -- 65.2664 68.2138 77.5504
Frequencies -- 83.8766 99.7639 120.2653
Frequencies -- 129.6693 135.4989 136.7736
Frequencies -- 158.1456 171.5800 181.6881
Frequencies -- 191.0469 199.6780 205.9402
Frequencies -- 224.1127 237.8521 249.0038
Frequencies -- 259.4552 269.6217 276.1063
Frequencies -- 297.3787 313.8587 320.4216
Frequencies -- 327.1536 331.2740 354.0944
Frequencies -- 356.9920 360.5514 373.5118
Frequencies -- 391.4575 393.2461 411.4374
Frequencies -- 418.0261 423.6480 427.8641
Frequencies -- 433.9333 448.5073 459.1706
Frequencies -- 462.4370 471.9117 476.4283
Frequencies -- 486.2535 497.1907 511.2103
Frequencies -- 538.4650 551.6671 557.7481
Frequencies -- 568.1513 580.9410 585.3787
Frequencies -- 611.6678 682.7045 694.5878
Frequencies -- 703.9046 712.3436 746.0255
Frequencies -- 785.2460 806.7788 815.9246
Frequencies -- 866.6353 895.4738 917.3628
Frequencies -- 925.3669 948.0990 963.4781
Frequencies -- 980.2798 1010.2636 1016.0781
Frequencies -- 1035.1494 1069.7266 1082.5393

Frequencies -- 1409.6713 1415.9258 1426.6762
Frequencies -- 1430.5242 1436.8047 1445.8576
Frequencies -- 1459.1332 1472.7546 1484.5779
Frequencies -- 1490.4559 1494.1521 1503.3965
Frequencies -- 1508.1223 1515.5545 1538.0342
Frequencies -- 1552.6363 1553.5746 1568.8515
Frequencies -- 1585.3685 1593.6038 1596.9800
Frequencies -- 1612.1711 1615.3357 1616.0619
Frequencies -- 1647.8978 1665.4108 1669.9704
Frequencies -- 1673.4795 1674.8526 1688.8260
Frequencies -- 1715.2257 1730.4395 1756.2785
Frequencies -- 1823.6955 1942.1787 2095.8884
Frequencies -- 2532.5972 3053.9264 3243.0292
Frequencies -- 3305.1549 3338.8824 3349.7934
Frequencies -- 3354.1865 3356.6476 3359.8771
Frequencies -- 3374.3335 3383.1340 3384.4403
Frequencies -- 3389.8919 3403.2196 3410.0040
Frequencies -- 3413.5588 3456.1337 3466.6814
Frequencies -- 3495.3065 3547.0182 3571.7751
Frequencies -- 3597.7490 3765.0724 3772.3006
Frequencies -- 3822.6430 3831.0378 3860.4037
Frequencies -- 3862.0419 3878.9714 3898.9929

Frequencies -- 1215.8401 1223.5231 1225.4212
Frequencies -- 1234.3280 1245.5191 1249.2984
Frequencies -- 1252.8025 1258.4478 1269.2460
Frequencies -- 1272.2668 1286.4388 1297.2777
Frequencies -- 1306.7999 1321.0881 1327.6436
Frequencies -- 1336.0198 1354.9768 1363.1166
Frequencies -- 1374.3194 1376.1785 1388.7210
Frequencies -- 1392.2726 1401.3832 1415.3511
Frequencies -- 1425.4509 1429.5753 1431.8692
Frequencies -- 1436.9666 1447.5054 1459.0017
Frequencies -- 1469.9441 1480.6618 1490.4096
Frequencies -- 1498.8096 1508.0500 1534.2550
Frequencies -- 1539.2342 1549.3855 1552.8797
Frequencies -- 1554.8095 1564.2765 1585.2492
Frequencies -- 1593.5559 1597.0997 1608.0646
Frequencies -- 1612.2520 1616.0992 1617.8667
Frequencies -- 1647.9542 1664.9848 1669.6713
Frequencies -- 1672.6425 1673.5596 1688.3018
Frequencies -- 1733.7606 1757.3851 1768.4893
Frequencies -- 1827.8025 1942.3858 2103.0419
Frequencies -- 2578.2619 2768.0146 3083.6767
Frequencies -- 3243.1786 3282.7688 3305.2352
Frequencies -- 3339.2837 3349.8903 3356.2295
Frequencies -- 3374.5207 3383.2586 3383.2868
Frequencies -- 3384.4722 3405.8490 3409.9526
Frequencies -- 3456.4341 3466.2824 3489.2809

Frequencies -- 1088.3072 1115.8665 1119.1118	Frequencies -- 3494.9975 3546.9706 3563.8104
Frequencies -- 1122.4339 1124.4107 1131.8269	Frequencies -- 3571.8068 3765.0813 3770.0036
Frequencies -- 1147.6301 1157.6180 1167.9295	Frequencies -- 3822.5354 3830.8452 3860.4040
Frequencies -- 1197.0696 1203.2272 1205.8439	Frequencies -- 3862.0865 3878.9347 3898.8458

204_a

TS

Frequencies -83.149 40.8299 51.3507	Frequencies 1218.1135 1233.7992 1268.5101
Frequencies 56.3809 85.4729 95.9258	Frequencies 1288.9091 1311.5268 1320.2551
Frequencies 158.5266 203.2504 228.9587	Frequencies 1331.1051 1358.8015 1371.6161
Frequencies 271.4808 288.2701 297.293	Frequencies 1387.3152 1399.6425 1440.0572
Frequencies 349.7001 381.8912 395.3935	Frequencies 1458.3688 1479.2436 1496.347
Frequencies 420.061 456.8845 465.4623	Frequencies 1510.043 1537.0902 1591.7416
Frequencies 500.7965 537.9729 573.2328	Frequencies 1598.2555 1610.4427 1624.5389
Frequencies 598.3854 633.9637 644.4457	Frequencies 1638.7596 1653.7143 1671.2154
Frequencies 710.1164 852.1735 883.0088	Frequencies 1722.2051 3331.5397 3358.7447
Frequencies 951.8211 980.3996 1030.1012	Frequencies 3377.1793 3396.7997 3399.2599
Frequencies 1077.5784 1097.2764 1104.1013	Frequencies 3403.3114 3435.435 3449.1509
Frequencies 1130.35 1135.5957 1143.6527	Frequencies 3527.8807 3560.7773 3775.9955
Frequencies 1170.369 1188.1046 1203.1437	Frequencies 3855.2343 3864.5103 3872.9622

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GS

Frequencies 43.6025 66.0161 78.5755	Frequencies 1233.1181 1250.2922 1270.7608
Frequencies 87.7877 103.0207 149.7533	Frequencies 1288.9694 1319.0479 1329.3913
Frequencies 169.901 195.0787 252.9852	Frequencies 1332.3722 1352.2756 1374.7827
Frequencies 281.7942 298.4799 350.0349	Frequencies 1389.908 1406.5189 1437.0694
Frequencies 382.3962 394.011 419.1949	Frequencies 1463.3328 1481.1204 1491.506
Frequencies 443.8139 461.0075 476.8764	Frequencies 1509.472 1534.5499 1593.6633
Frequencies 500.9934 543.2443 568.7953	Frequencies 1600.1127 1614.5622 1622.3033
Frequencies 603.4366 608.0225 641.187	Frequencies 1645.6294 1652.7129 1670.5733
Frequencies 711.3913 847.3917 884.4011	Frequencies 1722.413 3322.7729 3338.9507
Frequencies 948.2637 984.2938 1032.0678	Frequencies 3374.3259 3378.347 3393.8931
Frequencies 1080.2749 1095.076 1108.6224	Frequencies 3401.1087 3429.8673 3450.5306
Frequencies 1125.86 1139.1669 1146.8849	Frequencies 3525.1322 3557.2885 3776.7155
Frequencies 1171.43 1193.346 1209.4569	Frequencies 3793.6354 3863.8257 3869.9147

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Frequencies -22.4534 41.6061 59.5185	Frequencies 1217.8487 1244.2605 1264.4064
Frequencies 84.7615 110.8105 124.5151	Frequencies 1275.7857 1299.3917 1307.5705
Frequencies 133.9322 209.6075 221.9666	Frequencies 1323.1813 1332.6711 1362.6663
Frequencies 247.5951 275.1887 304.1215	Frequencies 1380.1755 1412.8512 1442.8415
Frequencies 329.0998 343.9398 396.2523	Frequencies 1451.1885 1500.194 1551.4465
Frequencies 427.6366 436.8372 476.0968	Frequencies 1562.188 1583.5694 1616.9794
Frequencies 496.7926 551.1116 565.6611	Frequencies 1622.8927 1651.5929 1661.1104
Frequencies 604.4265 631.0461 681.8853	Frequencies 1672.0041 1950.3633 2040.2905
Frequencies 716.2357 781.5697 834.2649	Frequencies 2083.9601 2339.6654 3365.6361
Frequencies 898.9612 934.0686 955.4661	Frequencies 3383.353 3401.9542 3414.8684
Frequencies 970.1112 1072.2934 1084.5237	Frequencies 3453.8053 3493.0745 3499.8205
Frequencies 1110.2813 1111.8409 1124.355	Frequencies 3522.6306 3543.5425 3570.7734
Frequencies 1153.3772 1166.4669 1176.7396	Frequencies 3846.6203 3864.214 3929.4192

366_bg_b**GS**

Frequencies	25.9586	30.3057	39.0861	Frequencies	1220.3	1229.1816	1233.9004
Frequencies	52.9535	65.613	73.2458	Frequencies	1248.6606	1258.1453	1262.45
Frequencies	83.3074	83.8679	91.5478	Frequencies	1272.3757	1278.6587	1287.9268
Frequencies	102.9793	107.5607	127.3773	Frequencies	1292.9287	1323.8593	1325.011
Frequencies	145.3272	148.1353	162.5776	Frequencies	1335.4371	1337.0965	1348.2138
Frequencies	185.246	203.9514	223.6243	Frequencies	1348.3975	1373.089	1383.2254
Frequencies	232.8929	261.5371	275.1194	Frequencies	1387.1072	1403.0129	1411.7647
Frequencies	291.587	293.0531	317.4357	Frequencies	1429.0818	1438.882	1443.3763
Frequencies	349.3324	357.8191	367.5571	Frequencies	1474.9816	1479.088	1483.6617
Frequencies	384.6656	401.9497	415.107	Frequencies	1494.9478	1509.6184	1523.3463
Frequencies	433.7779	448.3937	454.8542	Frequencies	1528.3657	1553.5146	1573.7159
Frequencies	462.6878	514.2053	515.6191	Frequencies	1603.525	1625.0114	1629.0022
Frequencies	535.3264	548.3979	569.7854	Frequencies	1657.3821	1661.9327	1665.2457
Frequencies	580.853	601.0918	605.5695	Frequencies	1670.1771	1678.9635	1691.6295
Frequencies	626.8261	652.5791	659.0239	Frequencies	1793.9587	1852.1102	1934.2295
Frequencies	697.286	718.3866	726.889	Frequencies	2835.8763	3211.1837	3303.7204
Frequencies	750.6918	786.3611	817.2577	Frequencies	3331.7947	3333.3958	3347.6219
Frequencies	894.491	922.7859	957.6033	Frequencies	3352.8589	3363.0982	3383.754
Frequencies	979.8221	994.1221	1018.0891	Frequencies	3384.8669	3393.8932	3400.9829
Frequencies	1049.0774	1065.8702	1090.4863	Frequencies	3439.4983	3442.3907	3450.2363
Frequencies	1102.1749	1110.0623	1127.1354	Frequencies	3547.2699	3568.1311	3578.8531
Frequencies	1129.5279	1142.9731	1155.805	Frequencies	3701.4235	3840.1417	3840.1687
Frequencies	1173.4587	1182.6988	1186.3146	Frequencies	3862.538	3865.6741	3878.6347
Frequencies	1198.3679	1208.7319	1213.5723				

366_bg_b**TS**

Frequencies	-44.9356	14.8647	37.4215	Frequencies	1208.6787	1210.9823	1214.0723
Frequencies	42.509	60.6651	65.0864	Frequencies	1233.4435	1247.7419	1256.1526
Frequencies	73.363	81.5797	90.3651	Frequencies	1263.1486	1267.4902	1277.4757
Frequencies	101.4425	105.3132	129.757	Frequencies	1283.2062	1292.9129	1320.3173
Frequencies	146.9874	151.1701	163.5764	Frequencies	1324.8546	1336.1511	1340.2337
Frequencies	183.7132	204.2754	220.3722	Frequencies	1345.449	1350.2533	1369.8114
Frequencies	230.4616	261.2152	274.218	Frequencies	1388.032	1403.8993	1409.2809
Frequencies	288.65	297.6144	316.2546	Frequencies	1429.217	1430.9938	1440.6466
Frequencies	349.5634	356.7876	369.0704	Frequencies	1451.122	1477.5509	1482.3154
Frequencies	383.1526	394.0906	404.1939	Frequencies	1498.2443	1512.1377	1523.6937
Frequencies	436.8297	445.5636	453.5206	Frequencies	1536.3313	1553.442	1573.5451
Frequencies	463.7846	492.1993	516.7396	Frequencies	1603.7382	1624.8592	1628.1096
Frequencies	536.4569	543.1159	555.1249	Frequencies	1634.9111	1660.853	1662.7726
Frequencies	568.2736	581.1086	600.8835	Frequencies	1671.1371	1679.1684	1691.2626
Frequencies	618.3408	653.0896	657.2315	Frequencies	1785.5005	1805.9959	1930.5531
Frequencies	697.6738	717.9811	723.8413	Frequencies	2853.3636	3107.0635	3236.7613
Frequencies	745.578	776.9724	811.7293	Frequencies	3300.2256	3331.6547	3333.3884
Frequencies	882.5169	895.5648	944.5371	Frequencies	3352.4736	3363.1114	3384.2728
Frequencies	974.0208	981.0259	988.2992	Frequencies	3384.8305	3393.339	3439.5491
Frequencies	1017.9478	1024.4071	1049.0399	Frequencies	3445.5459	3451.8316	3547.5638
Frequencies	1067.2578	1077.975	1098.8848	Frequencies	3568.5359	3590.3064	3701.1502

Frequencies	1112.3602	1129.0893	1131.4551	Frequencies	3832.0115	3839.9168	3862.4825
Frequencies	1141.4168	1165.3504	1167.9984	Frequencies	3865.6455	3878.4054	4186.6744
Frequencies	1178.4836	1195.4438	1203.0365				

366_bg_a (TS)

GS

Frequencies --	-4.9307	8.4574	22.3345	Frequencies --	1214.5749	1219.3804	221.2077
Frequencies --	49.1368	54.1026	69.9488	Frequencies --	1251.9545	1263.7923	1279.3452
Frequencies --	75.2588	91.4365	94.5491	Frequencies --	1289.3877	1292.5572	1304.8749
Frequencies --	98.2815	109.1768	141.7190	Frequencies --	1310.1541	1318.4136	1327.1136
Frequencies --	149.5172	172.8415	185.0804	Frequencies --	1334.3455	1346.2856	1362.2086
Frequencies --	191.7821	215.7116	230.9046	Frequencies --	1373.5989	1377.7269	1388.1464
Frequencies --	254.1190	260.8180	282.6270	Frequencies --	1399.9089	1402.1772	1416.0440
Frequencies --	302.1769	318.3630	323.8754	Frequencies --	1425.4172	1432.3678	1446.0277
Frequencies --	329.2228	346.4164	366.2170	Frequencies --	1463.7970	1477.5307	1483.2121
Frequencies --	376.2529	387.1861	408.8380	Frequencies --	1490.1360	1496.2097	1521.3581
Frequencies --	473.6645	499.3541	508.0666	Frequencies --	1523.1540	1540.0049	1586.2445
Frequencies --	530.1851	543.6365	556.0902	Frequencies --	1589.8663	1598.5147	1608.4467
Frequencies --	585.1495	607.4461	627.8549	Frequencies --	1628.7668	1634.1575	1634.7141
Frequencies --	630.1111	653.3372	654.7366	Frequencies --	1649.7943	1681.2463	1691.1668
Frequencies --	712.3703	741.6356	809.2007	Frequencies --	1693.9901	1721.8972	1724.9424
Frequencies --	859.7493	898.5468	931.8004	Frequencies --	3096.2866	3299.2894	3323.6401
Frequencies --	970.1236	982.8882	985.3951	Frequencies --	3329.3271	3347.3919	3360.4955
Frequencies --	1003.0511	1018.0210	027.7251	Frequencies --	3363.4261	3379.3762	3383.8356
Frequencies --	1054.8009	1090.2864	1100.3716	Frequencies --	3386.5864	3400.4742	3428.8643
Frequencies --	1107.9477	1112.2482	1133.7741	Frequencies --	3435.3116	3449.8732	3455.1858
Frequencies --	1145.1313	1152.1089	1161.3332	Frequencies --	3474.2413	3531.3154	3561.5355
Frequencies --	1173.3022	1181.7571	1191.3817	Frequencies --	3703.8170	3785.0054	3820.5074
				Frequencies --	3852.4662	3857.0601	3863.6855

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GS

Frequencies	1251.0698	1261.823	1276.2179	Frequencies	5.2275	19.0686	27.2194
Frequencies	1289.2191	1289.4368	1293.1245	Frequencies	52.9883	57.5483	68.2387
Frequencies	1317.9567	1320.2315	1333.803	Frequencies	76.3547	91.9533	94.8776
Frequencies	1337.1624	1346.622	1360.8929	Frequencies	100.9513	115.3598	141.9751
Frequencies	1370.0036	1373.0966	1387.2799	Frequencies	149.4536	172.5914	185.6816
Frequencies	1392.1684	1400.919	1409.5653	Frequencies	192.7529	217.8337	233.0051
Frequencies	1426.5775	1432.8556	1447.6452	Frequencies	255.2747	261.5329	283.8224
Frequencies	1459.0658	1477.4736	1483.3385	Frequencies	303.2888	318.2026	324.5955
Frequencies	1485.6922	1494.4498	1500.1656	Frequencies	329.771	348.6706	367.6716
Frequencies	1521.8209	1524.6184	1539.7578	Frequencies	376.9794	387.4155	410.6374
Frequencies	1589.8704	1598.0291	1608.4552	Frequencies	426.4045	437.3455	470.352
Frequencies	1628.4672	1634.1606	1635.0792	Frequencies	474.4631	499.8625	507.5972
Frequencies	1650.4278	1681.2589	1691.3404	Frequencies	532.0426	542.6912	558.3391
Frequencies	1694.1437	1724.4255	1728.0517	Frequencies	587.0159	608.9288	627.8287
Frequencies	3296.0814	3298.6845	3323.6192	Frequencies	630.6651	654.697	655.8752
Frequencies	3328.891	3347.1304	3363.41	Frequencies	712.535	741.9927	809.0302
Frequencies	3379.4673	3383.7728	3386.4476	Frequencies	860.894	893.281	931.1997
Frequencies	3394.6881	3400.8776	3405.4	Frequencies	969.1729	979.8408	982.5126
Frequencies	3428.8515	3434.962	3444.381	Frequencies	998.4857	1018.4187	1031.8474
Frequencies	3476.5432	3531.3416	3561.6246	Frequencies	1075.6982	1092.971	1105.2563
Frequencies	3703.6559	3783.9624	3820.4777	Frequencies	1111.3003	1124.3049	1138.2001
Frequencies	3852.4343	3857.0334	3863.669	Frequencies	1145.6006	1147.097	1163.1939
Frequencies	1198.4673	1214.2407	1216.2064	Frequencies	1174.278	1191.0874	1192.1549
Frequencies	1221.2132	1222.5838	1234.0885	--	--	--	--

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TS

Frequencies	-13.1158	12.0106	19.7969	Frequencies	1196.2414	1202.3995	1211.5521
Frequencies	29.0602	30.8699	34.7658	Frequencies	1213.7124	1216.9178	1221.0423
Frequencies	37.9935	41.8448	45.7613	Frequencies	1224.9755	1235.154	1242.4369
Frequencies	51.6683	56.1684	59.5013	Frequencies	1243.6965	1254.4192	1262.9318
Frequencies	61.5834	76.2417	85.7874	Frequencies	1267.2916	1274.6477	1280.31
Frequencies	93.6681	96.876	107.8614	Frequencies	1287.2609	1291.2349	1294.9124
Frequencies	112.382	115.5129	120.6224	Frequencies	1304.0401	1307.3042	1315.0773
Frequencies	129.4956	135.2914	139.788	Frequencies	1318.2828	1322.3222	1326.1637
Frequencies	152.0271	152.2877	156.7291	Frequencies	1326.7812	1335.0778	1348.9169
Frequencies	164.303	168.3063	186.7912	Frequencies	1350.8638	1356.8656	1363.3228
Frequencies	198.021	201.929	205.6935	Frequencies	1374.8496	1388.7732	1398.7568
Frequencies	216.6001	224.5204	229.1421	Frequencies	1401.4804	1410.1218	1412.1244
Frequencies	239.1671	248.7278	262.4075	Frequencies	1419.1499	1429.928	1436.6831
Frequencies	269.7552	279.3928	288.5317	Frequencies	1443.0602	1445.5088	1460.6477
Frequencies	295.763	306.8462	311.5214	Frequencies	1461.4006	1464.5228	1465.5114
Frequencies	324.8789	333.5945	347.0221	Frequencies	1483.0115	1489.1156	1490.5284
Frequencies	350.2529	364.2293	371.3448	Frequencies	1494.8162	1499.0882	1509.2682
Frequencies	371.8532	384.3936	396.3995	Frequencies	1510.7516	1515.9006	1523.4252
Frequencies	406.1547	420.5714	425.1025	Frequencies	1526.4806	1543.6549	1547.4836
Frequencies	434.406	444.1204	450.8311	Frequencies	1548.0279	1561.6172	1589.2533
Frequencies	459.087	470.9361	492.6334	Frequencies	1606.7741	1623.0354	1633.1845
Frequencies	505.7443	522.6358	525.4117	Frequencies	1637.2578	1641.3634	1642.4275
Frequencies	531.7796	545.4647	554.2693	Frequencies	1649.5175	1656.948	1659.2208
Frequencies	558.3388	578.8721	584.0606	Frequencies	1661.4355	1662.6016	1663.3782
Frequencies	596.3665	605.9313	618.1532	Frequencies	1673.322	1674.742	1684.335
Frequencies	626.8128	629.8126	643.3926	Frequencies	1692.7878	1703.6693	1714.8827
Frequencies	671.4201	679.495	694.44	Frequencies	1811.6083	1904.7282	1925.4973
Frequencies	703.5223	723.3388	742.8395	Frequencies	1946.3189	2114.4416	3305.766
Frequencies	752.5559	761.8307	769.8728	Frequencies	3324.6053	3325.3686	3328.9606
Frequencies	805.7855	806.3113	816.3497	Frequencies	3338.8603	3343.3485	3359.9171
Frequencies	835.1845	922.7402	934.2866	Frequencies	3361.757	3362.2471	3370.3336
Frequencies	938.7462	948.6871	953.9075	Frequencies	3377.0242	3382.494	3383.0052
Frequencies	954.9003	970.0085	1001.3559	Frequencies	3384.806	3398.5388	3400.6282
Frequencies	1018.5696	1029.0311	1034.8744	Frequencies	3418.8736	3427.0076	3430.6431
Frequencies	1035.3963	1045.975	1056.8307	Frequencies	3433.6149	3439.161	3443.4139
Frequencies	1066.7317	1074.1288	1074.8052	Frequencies	3446.911	3447.6553	3530.3168
Frequencies	1094.7205	1103.3653	1111.3071	Frequencies	3540.484	3542.3987	3543.6132
Frequencies	1121.8261	1124.184	1128.2445	Frequencies	3546.4644	3566.4866	3569.2073
Frequencies	1129.6511	1136.839	1142.6674	Frequencies	3623.5166	3715.7231	3729.1036
Frequencies	1146.0353	1157.6126	1176.2743	Frequencies	3799.228	3830.8374	3850.9391
Frequencies	1180.7457	1184.0673	1188.5692	Frequencies	3857.0957	3864.973	3880.4715

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Frequencies	-158.9069	37.8989	55.3429	Frequencies	1259.4103	1277.3268	1301.4572
Frequencies	71.0667	112.9801	129.8156	Frequencies	1322.2451	1324.7657	1356.1514
Frequencies	153.3436	168.9801	213.8861	Frequencies	1362.4236	1372.7217	1390.1329
Frequencies	240.3408	265.3073	279.7724	Frequencies	1397.5	1426.8152	1464.703
Frequencies	283.1028	315.593	348.4261	Frequencies	1468.8435	1480.6687	1497.8373
Frequencies	366.3084	385.2227	417.7279	Frequencies	1526.6717	1535.7253	1538.3391
Frequencies	441.3996	496.6478	513.1388	Frequencies	1557.9371	1604.7914	1616.5097
Frequencies	517.928	521.2702	567.2083	Frequencies	1621.6485	1645.0491	1652.6384
Frequencies	582.7707	615.7641	626.408	Frequencies	1660.6301	1689.8152	1771.7191
Frequencies	642.6445	659.8069	662.0575	Frequencies	1799.0948	1843.5533	1929.4487
Frequencies	685.9593	717.675	730.3053	Frequencies	2160.9667	2757.0444	3079.9223

Frequencies	752.9874	867.4621	876.7489	Frequencies	3183.8709	3342.9808	3399.4455
Frequencies	913.4226	916.6125	952.4305	Frequencies	3415.1096	3420.9977	3441.0186
Frequencies	978.0277	991.3461	1021.6953	Frequencies	3484.141	3507.805	3521.2975
Frequencies	1031.5314	1047.1179	1064.6973	Frequencies	3527.0077	3619.2594	3640.6573
Frequencies	1123.4557	1142.3203	1186.2969	Frequencies	3736.5533	3888.6575	3919.2876
Frequencies	1196.7972	1207.5871	1238.8121				

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GS

Frequencies	36.276	40.4582	66.4628	Frequencies	1188.1794	1194.7201	1224.9766
Frequencies	83.1669	113.9314	118.0372	Frequencies	1227.974	1247.214	1258.7111
Frequencies	159.4695	176.2633	214.4676	Frequencies	1292.2952	1315.8063	1322.4484
Frequencies	236.5482	264.7115	284.263	Frequencies	1335.3644	1344.6696	1374.9931
Frequencies	285.4945	326.8476	345.7591	Frequencies	1382.9803	1419.9514	1424.5626
Frequencies	361.3913	389.553	417.5552	Frequencies	1453.2446	1466.6717	1475.978
Frequencies	444.7576	498.2281	510.0349	Frequencies	1507.477	1513.9036	1535.8058
Frequencies	517.8232	522.276	560.8616	Frequencies	1540.8658	1559.5255	1607.7166
Frequencies	583.5645	617.1514	628.4847	Frequencies	1631.3971	1645.7018	1652.5411
Frequencies	640.9006	646.3118	664.5222	Frequencies	1660.5338	1688.5552	1770.4697
Frequencies	685.0006	717.3043	738.097	Frequencies	1812.7977	1929.1691	1968.0075
Frequencies	753.8167	875.1255	880.2061	Frequencies	2163.3129	2750.3085	3179.0722
Frequencies	917.0074	921.2859	957.1792	Frequencies	3343.8926	3398.5135	3415.8458
Frequencies	973.9652	994.0705	1022.9514	Frequencies	3417.3537	3422.3187	3447.4103
Frequencies	1029.8071	1045.6738	1062.9622	Frequencies	3484.36	3506.9994	3521.0768
Frequencies	1115.9276	1143.0259	1166.0349	Frequencies	3524.7779	3615.2626	3640.9207
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566_a

TS

Frequencies	-39.1917	4.2798	29.9023	Frequencies	1195.5615	1196.4837	1202.05
Frequencies	33.8634	39.6611	47.1483	Frequencies	1216.4054	1222.3665	1228.4021
Frequencies	55.0912	65.0749	71.3502	Frequencies	1229.47	1233.2844	1237.818
Frequencies	74.9778	85.399	94.3466	Frequencies	1248.5038	1255.1937	1266.8671
Frequencies	102.6711	108.307	118.1554	Frequencies	1290.5406	1298.7186	1305.4443
Frequencies	136.4848	149.636	155.0457	Frequencies	1308.72	1312.2538	1317.7288
Frequencies	162.1298	163.0896	171.9957	Frequencies	1330.8493	1334.4502	1336.1667
Frequencies	183.257	189.4596	211.9445	Frequencies	1340.474	1348.344	1351.5754
Frequencies	220.9081	224.1511	232.0586	Frequencies	1360.5608	1370.9553	1382.9409
Frequencies	245.6805	250.7145	275.6838	Frequencies	1390.5568	1399.3001	1413.777
Frequencies	292.2328	307.8305	313.4777	Frequencies	1418.0496	1425.969	1437.2258
Frequencies	322.9331	333.1864	344.6578	Frequencies	1443.6257	1449.4712	1452.786
Frequencies	354.1358	369.2579	371.8737	Frequencies	1456.3524	1462.5795	1463.5216
Frequencies	382.7647	388.5445	390.9324	Frequencies	1468.896	1479.7682	1496.9995
Frequencies	411.2364	428.4075	434.959	Frequencies	1499.5562	1506.6845	1513.5514
Frequencies	439.314	455.0009	467.7633	Frequencies	1521.8819	1556.3578	1559.5447
Frequencies	477.7484	482.3531	491.0047	Frequencies	1562.5809	1610.6067	1623.7762
Frequencies	501.4976	502.2022	523.4951	Frequencies	1636.8538	1644.2191	1648.7908
Frequencies	526.6346	542.8784	550.8786	Frequencies	1654.1568	1659.9815	1665.7187
Frequencies	566.4666	585.5986	594.822	Frequencies	1667.0131	1667.6092	1682.1773
Frequencies	601.3408	617.7972	621.919	Frequencies	1693.6254	1699.3846	1699.8738
Frequencies	638.1227	652.4827	668.1989	Frequencies	1710.9459	1823.6591	1852.6059
Frequencies	679.5412	683.3019	687.9925	Frequencies	1895.4504	1921.0862	1938.5752
Frequencies	725.8169	734.8893	748.597	Frequencies	1958.4833	2018.5029	2616.6346
Frequencies	755.6539	779.7861	784.1319	Frequencies	2823.1994	2946.7733	2965.7585
Frequencies	811.011	830.9332	858.9087	Frequencies	3297.9395	3300.3811	3345.4052
Frequencies	863.4168	904.8213	916.088	Frequencies	3359.0687	3365.9333	3380.9669
Frequencies	921.5007	933.1712	952.4196	Frequencies	3385.3623	3386.6745	3386.7294

Frequencies	961.935	973.465	1013.6631	Frequencies	3400.2743	3403.0955	3417.7904
Frequencies	1023.4563	1040.7184	1056.031	Frequencies	3430.4634	3433.7408	3434.3755
Frequencies	1074.7554	1079.691	1085.3803	Frequencies	3441.9998	3446.645	3477.136
Frequencies	1091.7782	1093.6105	1104.7904	Frequencies	3505.1903	3519.5321	3532.822
Frequencies	1108.3337	1114.1826	1122.2638	Frequencies	3545.0274	3549.628	3551.0849
Frequencies	1128.4829	1138.9523	1145.5097	Frequencies	3570.8449	3620.8881	3770.186
Frequencies	1152.5061	1154.6881	1158.4177	Frequencies	3829.0771	3907.0071	3909.7943
Frequencies	1169.7942	1175.644	1182.9664				

368 (GS)

Frequencies	27.2619	35.7245	50.9165	Frequencies	1266.8238	1272.7989	1279.3953
Frequencies	63.9293	74.1199	84.073	Frequencies	1310.0027	1312.7874	1335.06
Frequencies	101.5733	113.2787	116.7739	Frequencies	1342.2743	1346.0039	1351.6478
Frequencies	128.9252	133.4349	150.1004	Frequencies	1363.1438	1374.6902	1382.8643
Frequencies	175.8409	216.095	240.7695	Frequencies	1398.2595	1403.5085	1415.3819
Frequencies	253.1066	259.3441	277.0029	Frequencies	1424.1812	1438.0816	1448.2858
Frequencies	281.1865	290.3805	299.5805	Frequencies	1457.0255	1471.5982	1475.1099
Frequencies	316.3815	342.1017	356.7876	Frequencies	1484.7476	1486.1405	1493.0837
Frequencies	365.2337	375.5086	397.2122	Frequencies	1501.8047	1518.983	1524.2269
Frequencies	406.5296	413.7117	426.7886	Frequencies	1550.5826	1565.0453	1583.0031
Frequencies	438.3419	442.1481	455.9584	Frequencies	1596.3879	1611.9366	1613.9618
Frequencies	463.9657	483.6182	515.4657	Frequencies	1620.8127	1654.1891	1658.9422
Frequencies	523.4429	526.6752	555.0366	Frequencies	1660.683	1679.059	1710.4716
Frequencies	564.3643	581.0572	590.6548	Frequencies	1723.5039	1733.9379	1904.2095
Frequencies	749.867	765.481	875.4797	Frequencies	1994.6345	2487.7739	3312.4563
Frequencies	897.1028	948.0475	950.0932	Frequencies	3330.0599	3373.7244	3379.0406
Frequencies	961.0616	1002.7173	1020.5668	Frequencies	3383.1631	3384.3091	3388.6579
Frequencies	1053.5057	1068.3433	1072.6633	Frequencies	3392.0462	3398.2419	3419.0403
Frequencies	1079.1543	1101.3231	1106.2832	Frequencies	3432.1957	3432.9458	3433.0934
Frequencies	1115.7275	1122.7999	1130.6446	Frequencies	3444.2263	3503.0834	3536.6256
Frequencies	1149.857	1162.1418	1178.6099	Frequencies	3545.8042	3565.3131	3569.1275
Frequencies	1179.1555	1197.5123	1208.2986	Frequencies	3570.6049	3716.8675	3796.7509
				Frequencies	3871.336	3872.2499	3910.1646

368 (TS)

Frequencies	-53.8478	31.4666	40.8515	Frequencies	1197.6719	1200.2992	1213.6714
Frequencies	48.6873	67.339	98.6405	Frequencies	1224.0701	1231.2626	1234.8631
Frequencies	103.0476	109.6481	116.6093	Frequencies	1243.2021	1264.3677	1285.5608
Frequencies	125.7885	126.8099	151.5695	Frequencies	1301.746	1319.9308	1338.1793
Frequencies	183.3983	218.5976	236.9483	Frequencies	1342.3083	1345.1683	1358.4755
Frequencies	253.5017	259.5819	272.6935	Frequencies	1361.311	1376.2774	1392.4301
Frequencies	279.6815	290.8547	294.4059	Frequencies	1405.1438	1413.1608	1418.9473
Frequencies	316.0766	330.4666	343.0448	Frequencies	1426.731	1436.6959	1440.0621
Frequencies	363.7112	374.1923	396.1928	Frequencies	1458.778	1471.8693	1472.9309
Frequencies	405.1658	410.3397	416.5825	Frequencies	1479.2645	1492.9713	1500.1468
Frequencies	430.4035	442.1892	458.3995	Frequencies	1510.5422	1517.7313	1549.6595
Frequencies	461.6885	484.7733	516.1507	Frequencies	1565.2984	1582.6567	1591
Frequencies	520.1131	526.6017	552.1045	Frequencies	1612.1534	1616.3324	1620.6974
Frequencies	562.31	579.5036	582.1902	Frequencies	1627.7527	1658.3955	1660.5944
Frequencies	596.2959	610.3671	643.5967	Frequencies	1678.9391	1710.3097	1733.9713
Frequencies	682.9044	708.8647	743.4508	Frequencies	1734.649	1742.4975	1910.4201
Frequencies	762.4153	799.5663	876.6975	Frequencies	1985.2509	2477.1935	2486.0496
Frequencies	896.709	934.5211	947.3207	Frequencies	3128.955	3179.1754	3372.7573
Frequencies	970.7843	998.3232	1027.5899	Frequencies	3378.8502	3381.8174	3383.5995
Frequencies	1047.1988	1057.1055	1060.7463	Frequencies	3385.4551	3392.4512	3398.9837
Frequencies	1070.4278	1073.4253	1088.6647	Frequencies	3400.1455	3419.0444	3433.0371
Frequencies	1095.3675	1113.1017	1117.2428	Frequencies	3433.3609	3509.5556	3536.3998
Frequencies	1130.9843	1133.4154	1147.2525	Frequencies	3546.1388	3565.2446	3569.3089
Frequencies	1170.1792	1178.1953	1181.6801	Frequencies	3571.2565	3795.725	3871.5697
				Frequencies	3871.849	3909.9573	4094.3072

Table S8

Thermochemistry of oxonium ions of carbohydrates α L-Fuc, β D-Man, α D-Gal, and α D-Xyl at different theoretical levels at ground (GS) and transition (TS) states in gas-phase

	αL-Fuc					
	M062X/SDD		M062X/STO-3G		PM6	
	GS	TS	GS	TS	GS	TS
E_{ZPVE}	111.13136	111.03550	117.32459	116.85271	95.67177	96.04116
E_{corr}	0.187392	0.186217	0.197589	0.196560	0.163800	0.163126
H_{corr}	0.188336	0.187161	0.198533	0.197504	0.164745	0.164070
G_{corr}	0.142155	0.143357	0.150526	0.149998	0.115545	0.118521
ϵ_0	0.177099	0.176946	0.186969	0.186217	0.152463	0.153051
E	-535.383488	-535.375725	-528.699369	-528.698887	0.173833	0.177051
H	-535.382544	-535.374781	-528.698425	-528.697942	0.174777	0.177995
G	-535.428725	-535.418584	-528.746431	-528.745448	0.125577	0.132446
	βD-Man					
	M062X/SDD		M062X/STO-3G		PM6	
	GS	TS	GS	TS	GS	TS
E_{ZPVE}	114.88089	114.30942	121.17829	120.75249	98.09081	98.07402
E_{corr}	0.194061	0.192679	0.203951	0.203015	0.168331	0.167352
H_{corr}	0.195005	0.193624	0.204895	0.203959	0.169275	0.168296
G_{corr}	0.146360	0.146627	0.155998	0.155322	0.118477	0.120375
ϵ_0	0.183074	0.182164	0.193110	0.192431	0.156318	0.156291
E	-610.553389	-610.550567	-602.854177	-602.853657	0.116639	0.141402
H	-610.552445	-610.549623	-602.853233	-602.852713	0.117583	0.142347
G	-610.601090	-610.596619	-602.902130	-602.901350	0.066785	0.094426
	αD-Gal					
	M062X/SDD		M062X/STO-3G		PM6	
	GS	TS	GS	TS	GS	TS
E_{ZPVE}	115.28596	114.58047	123.31924	122.81380	98.44704	97.68119
E_{corr}	0.194354	0.193224	0.205845	0.204913	0.168472	0.166888
H_{corr}	0.195298	0.194168	0.206789	0.205857	0.169416	0.167832
G_{corr}	0.148355	0.147294	0.162305	0.161387	0.119792	0.119258
ϵ_0	0.183720	0.182596	0.196522	0.195716	0.156885	0.155665
E	-610.561507	-610.554374	-602.911207	-602.903563	0.120457	0.123706
H	-610.560563	-610.553429	-602.910263	-602.902619	0.121401	0.124650
G	-610.607507	-610.600304	-602.954747	-602.947088	0.071778	0.076075
	αD-Xyl					
	M062X/SDD		M062X/STO-3G		PM6	
	GS	TS	GS	TS	GS	TS
E_{ZPVE}	93.37618	93.13655	98.61998	98.28511	79.50297	79.15992
E_{corr}	0.157670	0.156942	0.165854	0.164445	0.136809	0.135458
H_{corr}	0.158615	0.157887	0.166798	0.165389	0.137753	0.136402
G_{corr}	0.115423	0.115110	0.123486	0.124174	0.090920	0.091757
ϵ_0	0.148804	0.148423	0.157161	0.156627	0.126696	0.126149
E	-496.103752	-496.102770	-489.869858	-489.858590	0.162975	0.163497
H	-496.102807	-496.101826	-489.868914	-489.857646	0.163919	0.164442
G	-496.145999	-496.144603	-489.912226	-489.898860	0.117086	0.119797

E_{ZPVE} – zero-point vibrational energy [kcal.mol⁻¹]; ϵ_0 – zero-point correction [Hartree.(partice)⁻¹]; E_{corr} – thermal correction to energy [Hartree.(partice)⁻¹]; H_{corr} – thermal correction to enthalpy [Hartree.(partice)⁻¹]; G_{corr} – thermal correction to free energy [Hartree.(partice)⁻¹]; E – sum of electronic and thermal energies [Hartree.(partice)⁻¹]; H – sum of electronic and thermal enthalpies [Hartree.(partice)⁻¹]; G – sum of electronic and thermal free energies [Hartree.(partice)⁻¹]

Table S9

D_{QC} parameters of equation (3) of carbohydrates α L-Fuc, β D-Man, α D-Gal, and α D-Xyl depending on the level of theory

Oxonium ions	D_{QC}		
	M062X/SDD	M062X/STO-3G	PM6
α L-Fuc	46.47193	419.8428	10.6504
β D-Man	133.3218	510.1424	30.2971
α D-Xyl	407.9304	52.03384	65.1469
α D-Gal	0.9402	741.547	236.892

Table S10

Experimental mass spectrometric measurable variables of glycan (8)

m/z	I ^{TOT} [arb.units]	m/z	I ^{TOT} [arb.units]
314.108063	2888.76754	1076.58411	1284.2261
366.175018	2381.26713	1078.59302	3040.7023
375.221008	3254.80507	1081.42603	669.498897
388.046051	407.264689	1083.44702	593.268475
486.304016	963.150973	1087.29211	6458.40899
504.230072	20324.9085	1090.64001	3332.81078
603.300049	7982.15128	1091.51807	3439.4319
610.526062	479.269803	1094.1261	1277.48346
635.277039	1569.6945	1098.22009	864.963013
657.215088	1744.13614	1101.14612	1079.45517
672.305054	456.331062	1103.91003	605.603583
676.577087	610.883667	1105.85303	972.416343
678.930054	420.054303	1107.38501	3428.66573
702.829041	587.417897	1112.60803	600.881417
712.136047	2495.55461	1120.57703	5757.88182
716.362061	8412.26214	1125.83105	1067.94743
719.732056	918.609134	1133.8501	1233.40939
727.002075	512.892951	1137.62805	602.419621
734.348083	1925.47753	1142.56104	3895.67077
762.616089	406.780813	1145.1571	3986.10356
767.685059	1212.97724	1147.57104	1268.04665
770.387085	424.845379	1149.12903	3701.97314
776.450073	2052.90461	1149.94507	2694.83792
798.200073	599.244406	1151.81702	5209.67133
805.368042	2794.2458	1156.16907	872.559897
811.437012	857.890967	1158.755	1188.0613
820.331055	1348.15746	1164.23706	455.339843
824.847046	743.328801	1167.05701	887.709051
827.493042	547.584452	1169.66602	445.616586
831.14209	433.723839	1172.48706	549.763337
833.87207	1469.95171	1175.74512	1386.89127
835.281982	417.823797	1180.95911	1151.08137
844.410034	9427.08764	1182.08911	844.278362
848.670044	469.076654	1183.37708	641.219964
853.412048	424.414877	1184.92908	1024.80846
858.005066	1284.97295	1186.59607	832.069113
860.58905	4236.47022	1189.31604	1871.2091
863.219055	497.308481	1192.24402	10444.9776
868.134033	761.931614	1199.23401	4742.42498
877.327087	1996.09691	1201.68103	879.625351
881.783081	653.285403	1204.73108	762.391119
883.200073	675.531947	1207.698	7951.36366
884.442078	610.988231	1212.69312	694.344262
888.858032	759.51868	1214.0481	1217.15683
890.587036	1767.55942	1219.724	1153.62515
897.157043	1603.87406	1220.71411	1258.10275
898.361084	785.169233	1225.81909	1047.65019
906.631042	3607.20246	1226.62402	1021.17605
909.750061	10085.9025	1229.20801	618.257865
918.492065	3393.61116	1231.76208	975.049803
922.71106	429.921953	1232.4751	964.648135
924.90509	897.358198	1235.33704	704.485902

927.023071	1348.53944	1237.64001	543.74498
930.243042	680.027726	1240.28406	2679.11493
931.434082	952.425614	1244.37012	1041.24544
932.486084	665.920604	1249.13306	9843.1707
934.588074	889.969619	1257.36304	16394.4375
940.600037	2556.26624	1262.56396	512.084924
942.255066	623.223199	1264.64502	4396.57644
945.387085	455.473601	1266.71704	3075.32046
949.090088	2998.84318	1271.87903	2967.31843
954.812073	1875.43625	1274.16809	2503.0459
957.577087	18919.2087	1279	1644.36525
964.442078	1607.89456	1283.97803	841.308222
967.521057	1502.43546	1286.01001	1273.94361
970.299072	805.123342	1294.0531	686.378789
972.098083	1062.21948	1304.59509	1042.43779
973.765076	1049.22971	1313.3031	3995.52881
979.035034	796.639644	1317.88611	521.327165
980.712036	665.969416	1321.89807	7261.66861
981.391052	671.897247	1339.87012	719.540285
982.96106	458.198682	1345.50208	794.470355
985.029053	911.618501	1351.74011	1370.63625
986.171021	957.562475	1358.22302	1212.70752
989.478088	4621.39819	1361.85107	992.644062
994.567078	2769.05332	1362.80505	506.808899
1006.39307	1545.82575	1364.474	946.052121
1014.36505	1003.9957	1369.61011	5513.15868
1018.06604	2128.72443	1378.69702	13053.4794
1022.24207	2410.34965	1404.31006	662.826651
1024.84302	813.52492	1408.55603	679.314138
1028.974	3523.90387	1413.70007	1292.02173
1030.68604	2770.0486	1422.69202	4098.0175
1038.14709	593.155671	1448.70605	991.217623
1040.66101	592.014469	1466.6261	3211.67472
1041.29504	556.209901	1470.08508	990.187687
1043.78906	408.040095	1552.6731	1051.29897
1045.33704	569.744122	1577.66809	760.061628
1046.81006	698.572877	1594.61804	932.553615
1048.82202	535.124123	1595.70911	750.971831
1050.56909	1168.28563	1666.86206	560.384994
1052.52905	1207.23464	1065.66406	822.925104
1055.01111	847.147751	1068.1781	895.687591
1058.5321	931.359776	1069.77808	1001.45213
1061.79102	694.638052	1072.37305	1031.34849
1074.39709	778.951572		

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